

HOLISTIC AND SUSTAINABLE APPROACH OF WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT IN MUMBAI SLUMS: ACHIEVEMENTS, CHALLENGES AND COMMITMENTS FROM THE DIARY OF PROJECT 'DAMINI'

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Abstracts:

Women empowerment is an area of debate over the decades, especially in Indian context. This paper attempts to analyze the exact means of women empowerment from an angle of holistic and sustainable development. The paper critically reviews the connection between economic independence and overall empowerment in Indian women under the scope of 'Damini', project for Mumbai slums women. In this paper woman empowerment is discussed under the shade of Sustainable Development Goals and the concept is assessed and synchronized with gender equality, sexual and reproductive health and rights, efficient decision making capacity and active involvement of family as integral components for complete women empowerment. Empowerment of women is essential in the process of upliftment of economic, social and political status of traditionally underprivileged women in Indian society. Development and empowerment for this group can only be attained by strategic planning, effective implementation and efficient monitoring. Scientific approach of policy making is the essential process of guarding the women against all forms of violence. The Paper is based on practical experience from the field and reports the general trend of challenges; Indian women are facing in the process of sustainable empowerment. The study reveals that women empowerment is incomplete unless the women are coming up with equal measure of social, political and economic rights, enjoyed by the male members in any community. The experience from 'Damini' concludes by an observation that women empowerment is beyond the theme of accessing education, food security and financial independence. Thus, 'Damini' shouts for technology based e-capacity building in women as their future strategy for the establishment of 'real' empowered women community in rural and urban India.

Keywords: *Women Empowerment, gender equality, sexual and reproductive health and rights, sustainable development goals, developing countries.*

"If you want something said, ask a man; if you want something done, ask a woman." — Margaret Thatcher

"A strong woman understands that the gifts such as logic, decisiveness, and strength are just as feminine as intuition and emotional connection. She values and uses all of her gifts." — Nancy Rathburn

The history of ancient India explains woman as an epitome of strength and worshipped in the form of Goddess. Modern Indian society is carrying this trend of worshipping but women are pseudo-empowered and in many places and states they are getting treatment of a second grade citizen. Numbers of initiatives taken by the Govt. and international policy makers is not sufficient to lower down the incidence of gender discrimination, gang rapes, acid attacks, sexual abuse, professional hustles, domestic violence etc. Moreover, the women are still struggling to earn its respect as a decision making individual in a family or in a society. Basic rights to sexual and reproductive health related services are not ensured in all sectors of India. Rural Indian women are even away from securing the basic right to their own bodies.

While analysing the situation in India, it is established that women's empowerment in India is highly dependent on many different variables that include demography, availability of basic livelihood support, literacy status, social status and biological age.

Throughout several past decades Govt. has made policies on women's empowerment exist at the national, state, and local levels in sectors, including health, education, economic opportunities, decision making, strategy formulation, gender-based violence,

and political participation. However, there are significant gaps between policy advocacy and real implementation in the community level. The increasing rate of female foeticide, killing of girl children, women trafficking, rape, early marriage, maternal mortality and malnutrition are the indicators of gender discrimination and unsustainable measure of women's empowerment.

1. Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) and Women Empowerment:

SDG 5 states about gender equality, most important factor in ensuring women empowerment and is essential for sustainable development. In India, one fundamental reason for gender inequality is strong preference for sons in a family that has led us to the female sex ratio of 918 per 1000 males according to NFHS-3. The ratio was 935 per 1000 males even during the NFHS-1. SDG 5 declares to "Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls".¹ To address the statement and implement it in community level, extensive participation of women in all sectors is needed. Moreover, rights to avail all services and freedom specifically in sexual and reproductive health is a challenge for Indian women and this drawback is pulling them down in getting empowered from social, mental and economic aspect. SDG 5 doesn't affirm sexual and reproductive health rights (SRHR) along with gender equality while talking about women's empowerment. In fact involving men in the process is more crucial to maintain the sustainability. Some other major issues are also political environment, policy transparency, financial support, monitoring and evaluation.

2. Damini in Urban Slums of Mumbai: An Initiative towards Women's Economic Empowerment:

"There is a stimulating buzz in the narrow by lanes of the suburban Mumbai shanties as we walk into one of the most unique classrooms you could have imagined in this setting. A group of women from the most vulnerable sections of the society, and some even HIV positive, quietly worked on sewing machines, as their boisterous teacher corrects and comments as she walks by each of her students. The products being created are a vivid ensemble of Indian dresses, children's wear, cushion covers, bags, wallets, and blankets. It is an endearing sight to watch them engrossed in their work as they flash a quick smile occasionally for our cameras." – The Alternative

Damini is an integrated project initiated by Ojus Medical Institute for the marginalized and oppressed women of Mumbai. The project focuses on employment generation for women living in the slums of Mumbai through vocational training. Apart from training them in courses like mehendi designing, tailoring and beautician skills, we also focus in educating these women about finance management, savings, how to open bank accounts, reproductive health, sexual awareness, importance of nutrition, managing adolescent health issues and maintaining child health. Damini targets school dropouts and women across Mumbai. The main focus of the project is life skill development for sustainable change. The program aims at ensuring financial empowerment of the women, making them self-sufficient in earning money to support their families or supplement their family income.

The project is 'By the women for the women', and it's a kind of a peer education by creating role models. According to Lata, "This project has given me respect and pride" and that's what 'Damini' does. Sustainability of the project is based on creating living empowered woman as the ambassador of women empowerment. Very unique feature of 'Damini' is the centres are designed in a user friendly way so the women feel comfortable and homely while attending the class. Damini is the low cost model for women empowerment in the lower income countries like Indian where lot more can be done by life skill development.

In broader aspect of the project is to catalyse holistic women development through skill training. The sustainable objective of the project is to make the women aware about their rights and making sure they are capable of securing those rights from family and society. Developing skills through personal development ignites creativity, installs the sense of achievement, insights intelligence and encourages team spirit. Personal development skills also provide self-confidence, the sense of self-respect and self-worth for the adolescent girls and women of the project. On the other hand practical vocational training skills open the window of opportunity and secure financial independence for women through self-employment. These changes in the women finally leads to a sustainable familial and social change, capabbling the women to place their own ideas and opinions in front of the society, coming up as an individual decision maker body and taking part in advocacy.

Case Study: 'Damini' Mansi

Mansi, a 22 year old young woman who is one the teachers at Damini, found out about

the organisation through some of her relatives and decided to attend the course. She would commute the long distance from her home to the centre everyday just for those 23 hours to be able to learn as much as she could. In the starting of her journey Mansi mentioned about her unequal position in the family. The deprivation and less importance from her husband and family members made her determined in securing the position as an empowered individual. She has spoken her heart out about no rights on taking decision for her own sexual and reproductive health life.

In the end, she secured the position of star student and after completing the course, we offered her a job at our centre as a teacher.

"I am happy that I am able to help the other women to become independent like myself by teaching them a new skill." – Mansi

Supporting Mansi's thought we are overwhelmed to mention that more than 3000 women were accessing the services of Damini program by 2010. Damini has expanded to 3 more schools ran by Bombay Municipal Corporation (BMC) and 2 slums centres wherein we conduct vocational courses such as tailoring, beautician, mehendi and computer classes.

Case Study: 'Damini' Lata

Title: Akka (Didi)-a True Inspiration

The Situation: Lata, didi/Akka for our girls in Damini is our teacher in our Nehru Nagar Centre, Mumbai, Maharashtra.

Introduce Your Hero or the Case under Study: Lata Akka, one of our teachers from Nehru Nagar. On an average day she is bustling with energy and zeal scolding,

correcting, laughing with her students. Over the years she has through her efforts gained a standing in her community in Nehru nagar. But Akka a few years back was not the same confident woman you see today. Back then she was one of our students in Damini, shy and lacked confidence. Originally from Tamil Nadu she was married to a man in Mumbai. Initially she was not allowed to pursue the course offered at Damini. With patience and persuasion she convinced her husband to allow her to come to Damini. From there her journey of self-discovery and building her confidence started.

She turned out to be an enterprising woman, who was keen to not only make a living but take her initiative to a higher level, something that none of her contemporaries ever voiced out. She talked about starting her own textile unit and still dreams about it. With hard work and perseverance she has now become a teacher at our Nehru Nagar centre and takes active participation in all our other activities as well.

Lata today is a teacher of our girls and women in Nehru nagar, is on her way to achieve that dream of hers and we at Damini would back her at every step.

3. Measureable Outcome of 'Damini':

The outcome of the comprehensive training is measured in both qualitative and quantitative point of views as follows –

Qualitative:

- Damini provides a space to these women to come and share and vent their feelings, which is an absent element in a city like Mumbai. They

seek the much required safe and private space, which gives them solace through these classes.

- Financial empowerment, a major component in the overall empowerment of women in every sense is achieved through the courses at Damini. Women leave Damini after the completion of the courses with a sense of achievement and high self-esteem and armed with the capacity to be a financial contributor for their families.
- Besides financial empowerment, various other trainings have empowered them as they know about their rights reproductive health, health as such and about the saving and investment options.

Quantitative:

- Since 2004, Damini has empowered almost 6000 slum women in holistic development.
- Around 60% of students start earning around 1000 to 1200/- within 3-6 month of passing the course.

4. Discussion:

SDGs, Affordability and women empowerment in India:

2016 marks the beginning of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and national governments are struggling with how to implement them to get optimum outcome. Global Aid donors are also planning the best strategy to get partner with the national Govt. for best outcome by 2030. While planning this, the most important and largely

unanswered rising question is how much will the ambitious SDG agenda cost, and can developing countries afford it? The Overseas Development Institute (ODI) reports that calculates the cost, availability and affordability of achieving three key SDG targets – ending extreme poverty, attaining universal primary health care, and attaining universal secondary school completion by 2030 – on a country by country basis. These basic three criteria are of utmost importance while talking about women empowerment in developing countries like India.²

Recently an UN Intergovernmental Committee of Experts estimated the total cost of the SDGs to be “trillions of dollars a year”.³ While this provides an indicative global estimate, it does not directly translate into how much the SDGs will cost in each country or whether they are affordable. The total cost for the SDG targets related to poverty, health and education is estimated to be US\$148 billion a year in low income countries alone. This is based upon the total poverty gap in each country, which is the amount of money required to bring all poor people above the extreme poverty line, as well as health and education costing data sourced from Chatham House and UNESCO respectively.

According the UN report, the chart below shows the annual per person costs on a country by country basis for low and lower middle income countries. Unsurprisingly, the cost of ending poverty is highest in poorer countries (blue area). Education and health costs (green and orange areas respectively) tend to rise as countries get richer.

Fig 1: Cost of poverty, health and education SDG targets in LICs and LMICs

Does Economic Empowerment Alone Ensure Holistic Approach of Women Empowerment?

Economic empowerment is the capacity of women and men to participate in, contribute to and benefit from growth processes in ways which recognise the value of their contributions, respect their dignity and make it possible to negotiate a fairer distribution of the benefits of growth (Eyben et al., 2008). Economic empowerment enhances the opportunity of women's access to economic resources and facilities including employment, financial services, property and other productive assets, skills development and market information. ⁴But, being financially independent is not sufficient to ensure holistic approach of women empowerment. Women's empowerment is a process of personal and social change through which they gain power, meaningful choices and control over their lives. ⁵ Gender quality, general health, sexual and reproductive health and rights, personality development, control over decision making, support of the family and adaptation with the

situation are very strong components of holistic and integrated women empowerment. A qualitative survey from Mumbai, India reports the connection between general and sexual health status of woman and effective empowerment. The study concluded that empowered, non-pregnant women in a predominantly patriarchal society constantly battle gender inequalities, which results in greater somatic symptoms. ⁶

5. Challenges:

There are several constraints that check the process of women empowerment in India. Social norms and family structure in developing countries like India, manifests and perpetuate the subordinate status of women. One of the norms is the chronic rate of female foeticide in almost all societies and communities. The society is more biased in favour of male child in respect of education, nutrition and other opportunities. Poverty is the reality of life for the vast majority women in India. It is another factor that poses challenge in realizing women's

empowerment. Education, poverty, preventive-promotive-curative health, antenatal care, lack of sexual and reproductive health and rights, dominating attitude of men, gender equality are some key challenges for Indian women even in the higher strata of society. While 82.14% of adult men are educated, only 65.46% of adult women are known to be literate in India. Poverty is considered the greatest threat to peace and optimum health in the world, and eradication of poverty should be a national goal as important as the eradication of illiteracy. Due to this, women are limited as domestic helps. The health and safety concerns of women are paramount for the wellbeing of a country and are an important factor in gauging the empowerment of women in a country. However there are alarming concerns where maternal healthcare is concerned.⁷

Damini also faced several challenges in ensuring effective empowerment of the women involved in the project. The main challenge is the change in attitude of the family members towards women involvement in social and economic reform. Other measurable challenges in the project are lack of fund to upgrade the course and incorporate latest technology in the training procedure. The employment generation is retarded because of availability of modern technical support and social marketing. Another very important concern is that often, Donors give more importance to the child project than the woman project.

Vision, Commitments and Sustainability in Women Empowerment:

The SDG 2030 agenda by UN shouts for 17 specific goals in ensuring sustainable development and women empowerment

including, ending poverty, ending hunger, ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all, achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls, achieve access to adequate and equitable sanitation and hygiene for all and end open defecation, paying special attention to the needs of women and girls and those in vulnerable situations, Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all, make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable, take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts, Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development.

In Indian context, promoting education, eradicating poverty, ensuring safety, successful implementation of policies, upgradation of existing national program and effective monitoring are crucial for ensuring sustainable women empowerment. But, the most important aspect of women empowerment in Indian context is gender equality and involvement of men in the procedure of ensuring equality. Access to sexual and reproductive health services for all Indian women, ensuring sexual and reproductive health and rights, right to body, eliminating all forms of violence against all women and girls in the public and private spheres, including trafficking and sexual and other types of exploitation, enhance the use of enabling technology, in particular information and communications technology, awareness generation and involvement of families are indispensable to reach the goal of optimum empowerment. These criteria can ensure women's full and effective participation and equal opportunities for

leadership at all levels of decision- making in political, economic and public life.

Damini also has strategized a detail measurable work plan to promote sustainable-holistic empowerment for the trainees. The project has planned to make the project technology based and e-friendly. Use of technology, mobile application and full access to social networking are thought to be incorporated for making the training comprehensive, smooth and easy to execute as technology based approach is of most importance in getting along with the current era of development. E-capacity building and management real time data are the most important agenda what Damini is looking for.

6. Conclusion:

"There is no chance for the welfare of the world unless the condition of women is improved; it is not possible for a bird to fly on only one wing." – Swami Vivekananda

Women empowerment means emancipation of women from the vicious grips of social, economical, political, caste and gender-based discrimination. It is recognized that Indian women have made an appreciable progress in almost seven decades of Independence, but the process is incomplete and partial. India positioned 29th among 146 countries worldwide on the basis of Gender Inequality Index. ⁸A total of 2,44,270 incidents of crime against women (both under IPC and SLL) were reported in the country during the year 2012 as compared to 2,28,650 in the year 2011 recording an increase of 6.4% during the year 2012.- *Sarojini Naidu*

In current situation, to create a sustainable-holistic model of women empowerment, basic human rights has to be ensured irrespective of the women's economic, social and political position. The initiative 'Damini'

strongly promotes the principle of ensuring rights of women and adolescent girls apart from economic independence under the scope of Sustainable Development Goals for optimum and long term women empowerment. 'Damini' looks for accessibility of all sexual and reproductive health services to the community women adolescent, specifically rights to their body. The women are counselled to place their opinion in decision making. The project also enlightens on the fact of involving men in generating equality in all strata of society. To keep pace with the current trend of globalization 'Damini' peaches e-based empowerment for all women. Strategic implementation of programs, monitoring, gap analysis and effective presentation of data are important to areas to focus on under the project. 'Damini' thus, looks for overall development of a woman to create self-confidence, self-esteem and self-worth in each and every woman in the society.

References:

1. Hoornweg D, Hosseini M, Kennedy C and Behdadi A. An urban approach to planetary boundaries. *Ambio*. 2016 Feb 20. [Epub ahead of print]
2. Can developing countries afford the SDGs? 2016. DEVPOLICYBLOG-From the Development Policy Centre. Available from <http://devpolicy.org/can-developing-countries-afford-the-sdgs-20160209/>. Accessed on February 2, 2016.
3. Brolan CE And Hill PS. Health Policy Plan. Universal Health Coverage's evolving location in the post-2015 development agenda: Key informant perspectives within multilateral and related agencies during the first phase of post-2015 negotiations. 2015 Oct 22. [Epub ahead of print]
4. Women's economic empowerment. 2016. Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. Available from <http://www.oecd.org/dac/gender-development/womenseconomicempowerment.htm>. Accessed on February 4, 2016.
5. Progress on women's empowerment: from technical fixes to political action. November, 2014. Working and discussion papers. Available from <http://www.odi.org/publications/8996->

- progress-womens-empowerment-technical-fixes-political-action. Accessed on February 10, 2016.
6. Davisa LM, Schensulb LS, Schensulc JJ, Vermad R, Nastasie BK, and Singhad R. Women's empowerment and its differential impact on health in low income communities in Mumbai, India. *Glob Public Health*. 9(5), 2014, 481–494.
 7. Shettar RM. A Study on Issues and Challenges of Women Empowerment in India. *IOSR J Bus and Man*. 17(4), 2014, 13-19
 8. A Critical Assessment of the UNDP's Gender Inequality Index. *Feminist Economics*. 19(2), 2013,1-32
 9. Kaur R and Garg S. Addressing Domestic Violence Against Women: An Unfinished Agenda. *Indian J Community Med*. 33(2), 2008, 73–76.

Formalising the Quandary of the Informal sector: A Study of the Female Hawkers in the Local Trains of Mumbai

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Abstracts:

Our employment industry is divided into the formal and informal sectors. The formal sector being the vital forms the mainstream which is monitored by some form of the government. Whereas the informal sector is seen to breed on a hand to mouth survival to exist that depends on no authority. The informal sector involves men and women who engage in different jobs which include beggary, shoe shiners, rag pickers, hawkers on streets etc. These informal errands provide economy for the poor who engage in such work. The struggle of existence for this population breeds inequality, poverty, helplessness, livelihood concerns etc. Such situation calls for a socio-anthropological study so as to mainstream their plight and provide the informal sector with better facilities and recognition. The paper addresses this concern with reference to the case of the hawking community with special attention to the female hawkers in the local trains of Mumbai. This paper explores the realities of train hawking and the plight of female train hawkers. First it looks at the dynamics of their business and highlights their daily struggle for security and survival. Followed by examining the train hawkers as part of the unorganized sector and the need for regulation of employment that would assure them security and independence. An analysis of the legal status of hawkers in India and their right to livelihood is made to understand their struggle with the government.

Through primary, secondary resources and transient ethnography, this paper would seek to validate its stance about questioning the existing inequality created between Hawking as a means of earning livelihood and mainstream employment in India which is inherently discriminating and the legislative interventions of the system which would fail to deliver if they are not audited in a timely and adequate manner. In conclusion, the paper would make a critique of the existing systems and offer a few suggestions and practical ideas for betterment of train hawkers especially through a contribution that can be made by civil society and some that could be taken up for further discussion.

Key Words: *Informal, Mumbai, Train hawkers, Unorganized Sector, Women*

The paper explores the essential presence of train hawking in a city, which requires a critical understanding of the functioning of public space. It places the female hawkers in train against the backdrop of informal sector in India. The experiences of hawkers in Mumbai, as elsewhere in India, has taught them not to fear a dictatorial state, but a voracious one, a state that constantly demands bribes and threatens demolition, against which a license provides security. For this paper, female train hawkers in the ladies compartment of the Mumbai local were interviewed for a brief period of six months almost every day on the researcher's to and fro journey to college. Data was collected by venturing into the markets, gathering joints of hawkers and by observation on various occasions and other public spaces. The issues and reflections from this ethnographic experience will spell out the issues and situations of the train hawkers. The paper uses the experiences of the female hawkers and generalizes their issues to larger community of train hawkers including both male and female. Although the female hawkers being more on the vulnerable side face issues related to their gender and also their work.

Most working class population in Mumbai use the local train as means of transport to commute to their work places. Hence, the frequency of trains across the three lines: central, western and harbour is quite high in Mumbai. Even though the frequency between two trains is a gap of two to three minutes, the trains are over flowing with commuters at peak hours. In such a scenario, train hawkers are most often seen as the less significant and unwanted human beings that need to be removed for the hygiene, safety

and comfort of more important human beings in the local trains.

Avek Sen describes, "They are illegal to the courts, inconvenient for the authorities, necessary for parties and unions and thus they are seen as categories of hawkers and beggars, divested of history and identity and hence of rights and needs. Their presence is acknowledged when counting them up for surveys, and when they have to be represented in law, policy, unions and quotas. These are some of the country's most vulnerable and, in every way unrepresented people thrown to their own resources in devising what they do for a living". The hawkers have a passion for economic self-reliance. Their existence is hand to mouth. They are in a profession that involves an endless daily fight for survival. Certainly not because of low sales or low profit earnings but the fear of losing their hard earned money to railway police and officials within a selfish system that cares not for the betterment of the marginalized.

Those that hawk in trains in Mumbai buy their stock of goods daily from wholesale markets in the city, a popular one located at Kurla¹ among others like Crawford, Natraj, Dadar etc They buy beauty and make up items, decorative accessories, stationary, brushes, toiletries, cutlery, food etc all at a rate of rupees five, ten, twenty and maximum of fifty and make a profit of two or three rupees on each item. The goods they sell are entirely their choice and are many times they are left with unsold goods. Seventy-five percent of their daily earning goes into investing goods for next day's business while just twenty-five percent is saved. They carry

¹ A station located on the central railways of Mumbai.

on trade with perpetual fear of encountering a cop at all times and are constantly at risk of losing their earnings to railway officials. They are made to pay a fine of rupees one thousand and two hundred on being caught besides this they are robbed by officials, their goods are confiscated which leaves them in debts sometimes of thousand of rupees.

Thus there is no account of the millions of illegal bribes that are paid and this is one major reason for not issuing them licenses to function. There are complete hierarchies of police and railway that thrive on these illegal earnings. The condition of the train hawkers is comparatively worse than the street vendors who now at least hold permits from the municipal corporation in Mumbai to hawk at the places allotted to them on streets. Also identity cards for street vendors which serve as licences are also being issued against a registration process and payment.

In a category which they don't belong to as against the street vendors because trains fall under no hawking zones. There are different ways that train hawkers carry on their trade. There are those who have their *Maliks*² or bosses, this group includes mostly young children hawkers and those that sell food items (*Vada Pav*³, groundnuts, *bhel*⁴, homemade sweets, *chikkis*⁵) and other items. Today nearly all train hawkers invest in goods themselves and sell them. The once existing mafia that bullied them no longer exists. The Police claim that they let child

hawkers continue their work without charging heavy fine so that they do not take to vices like drugs etc. for survival. They ask them for favours, small ones like boot polishing, etc. instead of money.

1. Female Hawkers

Female train hawkers are the most commonly found in the hawkers category and these include young girls, teenagers, middle aged women, mothers and some old aged women too. These are generally those women who have taken up hawking either due to tradition or those who see it as a convenient option to help their family survive. In this daily routine the female hawkers are involved in other risks along with those related to their work. Some of which is for mothers who carry their babies on them and enter the crowded train and also jump out when the train takes off. The risk of slipping off the train with the child is so high here. They ensure that their baby is generally sleeping during their hawking hours in the train; babies are even drugged to sleep so that they don't trouble their mothers at work. In the case of small girls who come selling goods when asked if education or going to a school was important, their reply is 'the money that she earned wasn't sufficient to meet the food expenses of the family'. Hence studying in a school is a far away dream for the young girls. Old aged women usually hawk as they have to earn for themselves with nobody to depend on in their family. These are the ones who usually give in to the bargaining done by the other lady commuters in the train. There are even male hawkers seen in ladies compartments in the trains. This is because women are seen as good targets for purchasing female related goods and for some it is just a mere occupation.

² A term used in Hindi which refers to one's owner or In charge.

³ It is the local Mumbai snack. It resembles a burger.

⁴ A puffed rice dish with various vegetables and a tangy tamarind sauce.

⁵ A traditional Indian sweet prepared with any edible nut or puffed rice or with mixed nut and sugar or jaggery.

2. Convenience or Crowding

The only issue on train hawkers raised by the Media so far is the 'convenience versus crowding' debate. Hawking of goods in Mumbai's suburban trains is strictly prohibited but in effect the entire railway system stretching across three separate lines (Western, Central and Harbour) are like a giant supermall on wheels that cater daily to 6.1 million commuters more appropriately read as customers (Indian Express, 1993).

For a group of women commuters en route from Churchgate to Virar⁶ the three hour journey to and fro daily, the hawkers on trains are their regular vegetable vendors and grocers because it is difficult to make time for shopping at the end of the day after the hectic work. These days the vegetables, dry fish and sometimes also fresh fish come cleaned, cut into pieces and ready to just be cooked. The flip side of the coin is that overcrowding in these trains has grown to such an extent that 4700 passengers are travelling per nine car train during peak hours as against the rated carrying capacity of 1700 thus making the presence of these hawkers extremely undesirable (Asian Age, 2005). Commuters complain that they have to make their journey in the company of beggars, eunuchs⁷, middle aged men and scrawny urchins but these very same commuters buy goods from them. According to the railway officials, the hawkers are a menace and it is not the railways job to provide them with a livelihood. They also argue that it is the commuters who are responsible and that the presence of hawkers

continues only because commuters carry on to buy goods from them.

Most commuters believe that hawkers enter into suburban trains for free except on occasions when caught by the police. In reality they have to pay hefty sums to police to hawk within trains. Hence they choose to operate within specific areas. For example if they hawk between *CST* (Chatrapati Shivaji Terminus) and *Byculla*⁸, they pay the railway police at *CST*. If they go beyond this fixed area they have to shell out to police at every station. The researcher witnessed an instance where a first class commuter created havoc in the entire compartment when a hawker selling earrings and clips entered. She threatened her saying that hawkers are forbidden from entering the first class compartment and asked people not to buy her commodities and hence forth boycott all hawkers.

There is constant passing of the buck of responsibility of protection from hawkers between the GRP (Government Railway police), the ticket collectors and the RPF (Railway protection force). The GRP is posted to ensure law and order at railway stations and are often blamed for the current state of affairs, the RPF claim that they are only concerned with the protection of Railway Property. The Railway Act that empowers the Railway personnel to take action against trespassers claim that their job is to only check the credentials of passengers and hawkers are the GRP's responsibility. But the steady income generated from *haftas*⁹ feeds the pockets of all the authorities within Railway Police hierarchies thus

⁶ They are names of railway stations on the western line.

⁷ They are locally known as *hijras*.

⁸ They are names of railway stations in the Central line.

⁹ It is a local term used for bribe.

allowing an entire corrupt system to thrive on the earnings of these victims.

3. Through the unorganized sector

Hawkers form a large portion of the urban informal sector. The First Indian National Commission on Labour (1966-69) defined 'Unorganized sector workforce' as "those workers who have not been able to organize themselves in pursuit of their common interest due to certain constraints like casual nature of employment, ignorance and illiteracy, small and scattered size of establishments". There are two sets of people that make female hawkers. One is the urban poor migrants from villages who come as economic refugees and possess low skills and lack education required for the better paid organized jobs and hence informal sector is their only means of survival. The second group is those whose spouses were once engaged in better paid jobs in the formal sector, most of them in the mills in Mumbai and Ahmedabad in the state of Gujarat and engineering firms in Kolkata, which have lately closed down. Hence the women of the household pick up trivial jobs to keep the subsistence alive and train hawking being one among them.

The unorganized sector has lesser control over resources and socio-economic power but its contribution to output and employment is greater than the organized sector. Despite a large social role that the unorganized sector plays in terms of production and employment, it is resource and income poor, with limited voice in public affairs and no voice in issues concerning them. This has serious effects on income and wealth distribution, sharing of

socio-political power and the nature and place of India in the global economy (Social Scientist 2003). This unorganized sector of small entrepreneurs and workers which forms a very huge section of the population provide a large part of the market for the mass production, modern sector non-agricultural consumer goods as well as for intermediate and consumer goods.

The total employment provided through hawking becomes larger if we consider the fact that they sustain certain industries by providing markets for their products. A lot of the goods sold by train hawkers, such as moulded plastic goods and household goods, beauty products and cosmetics, homemade sweets, snacks, jewellery, stationery are manufactured in small scale or home-based industries. These manufacturers cannot afford to retail their products through expensive distribution channels of the formal sector. In this way they provide a valuable service by helping sustain employment in these industries. Thus they are a vital link between producers and consumers making a valuable contribution to the economy.

The unorganized sector as an indicator of underdevelopment is treated as a transit category which is expected to disappear with development. The most distressing part is the lack of social security for all the unorganized sector workers in most developing countries. According to the Tenth Five Year Plan (2002-2007), of the 400 million workers in the country, only 50-60 million, i.e. 12-15%, are covered by some form of social security.

Portes and Haller, in their definitive book, 'The Informal Economy' defines Informalisation as 'a process of income generation characterized by one central feature: it is unregulated by the institutions

of society, in a legal and social environment in which similar activities are regulated'. Thus the key difference between a purse/bag sold on the train and an expensive branded bag is that the former sell unbranded products without paying taxes. The informal economy thus functions as a shadow economy (Fredrick and Colin, 2013), producing legitimate products but without the sanction or protection of law. Though it is unregulated by the state, the informal sector often functions with implicit permission from state institutions, although usually in illegal ways. For example, hawkers are unlicensed, but they pay the insignificant bureaucracy huge amount of money per year in bribes.

The descriptions of the informal sector by Hernando De Soto in his work, 'The Other Path' (1989) says that the multitudes of unorganized self-employed workers in the informal economy, such as the local cobbler, rag picker, fishmonger, vendor, florist, pawnbroker, etc., are brave 'entrepreneurs' who routinely oppose stifling state regulation. De Soto considers government regulation of the informal economy as intrusion upon their enterprise. Hence the regulation of employment conditions must entail that employment must be permanent and as per law and that social security be guaranteed by providing insurance coverage for illness, maternity, property, disability, old age, and death must be attached. Regulation of this sector is seen as a solution to make them a part of the development process.

4. Legal Status of Hawkers

The essence of the problem of Hawking lies with legal systems. Law requires them to have a license to hawk and without this slip of paper they are illegal, trespassers and

criminals that disregard law. Law gives an unlimited power to corrupt officials who use it to their benefit, very often illegally. Law that is meant to empower divests them of all moral and human rights of survival and progress. The Constitution of India, The Municipal Corporation Acts of various states, the Police Acts and the Railways Act affect the functioning of hawkers. But except the Constitution of India all other acts were framed under the British rule and by the Britishers keeping in mind their futuristic goals and ideas of perfect cities to remain on par with their western counter parts.

With the formation of the Municipal Corporation street hawking earlier administered by trade guilds was brought under the Corporation's regulatory powers. Hawkers thus had to procure a license to function in the cities, something they did not have to do earlier. Thus the issue of legality of hawker only by holding a license was introduced in Indian cities. The legal status of Hawkers is a very grey area. As per the Constitution of India they are perfectly legal but as per the Municipal Corporation Acts, Railway Act and the Police Acts they are illegal without a license.

In 1989 the Supreme Court gave a major judgement (Sodhan Singh vs. NDMC). It ruled that every individual has the right to earn a livelihood as a fundamental right. Hawking is thus a fundamental right provided it does not infringe on the rights of others. This makes hawking legal but requires hawkers to have a license for carrying on their business. Train Hawkers have been pleading to the government for the license that has been given to boot polishers at the stations that allows them to carry on their business for ten or twenty rupees paid

to the railways daily, but their pleas seem to be falling on deaf ears.

There are therefore two sets of influences controlled by two different groups of people. One is the practices and dynamics of trade and the market place in which hawkers are vital as they contribute to GDP (Gross Domestic Product) and the other is the legal provisions in which hawkers are to be regulated and controlled. Thus there are traders and small businesses on one hand and the Railway Police and Police Department on the other.

5. Attitude of the Authorities

According to the Mumbai Hawkers Union, Train Hawkers in Mumbai are known to unite temporarily with backing from the Mumbai Hawkers Union in times of adversity and when draconian issues and laws concerning them arise. This tentative solidarity ceases when things get better and they return back to work. This union has organized a number of protests, demonstrations in the past asking for licenses, amendment of laws, fines etc. The Mumbai Hawkers Union has written letters of protest on behalf of hawkers to those in authority for similar reasons.

The researcher was told by a train hawker that their unions are in name sake only. Their unions do not do what hawkers really want and choose to work at the surface level. What train hawkers really want is backing and union intervention when they are caught, threatened or their goods confiscated. They want their unions to free them in times of real trouble. The *morchas*¹⁰ according to them only worsen their already bad condition

and put them in bad terms with authorities. The Mumbai Hawkers Unions and those that run it make things hard for train hawkers when it asks them to go through formalities like registering as a part of the union etc instead of providing the actual help needed. The moderate ways of letters, applications, and permissions fails to give any hope of betterment to these hawkers and only weakens their trust and faith in the capacity of a union.

The government has set aside no hawking zones with a fine of rupees five thousand to hawkers that are caught in these zones. Trains come in the no Hawking zones. This puts train hawkers at a greater risk of encountering officials that may threaten them with such a huge fine taking advantage of the rule. This leaves the train hawkers in this city with no union support, and no government support and at the mercy of these organizations.

There is unity among them but unity with fear. Train hawkers fear that getting together by themselves will worsen their plight if it comes to the notice of police. They fear they will not be allowed to work besides being harassed even more. With a hand to mouth existence and daily struggle for survival it leaves them with little time and no courage to unite and fight. They live today with an attitude that the only way out it is the goodwill of the government and goodwill of their union. The government and union can do all it takes to better their conditions if they really want to.

¹⁰ It is a Hindi term for Protests

6. Conclusion

Given the realities of train hawking and the government apathy suggestions for betterment of train hawkers need to be practical in the sense that they are implementable and not implausible. It is necessary to know how many people are actually employed in this profession and hence registration system is needed, that provides information to the government. With such a system in place the government can get an idea of the number of persons engaged in this activity and release these figures with a certain number of licenses. Hawkers who do not see hope of getting a license will automatically disperse to other urban areas and this will help prevent overcrowding of hawkers in metropolitan cities. Besides their right to profession as a human and fundamental right must be recognized as hawking within trains or on the streets is not immoral and against societal norms.

SEWA (Self Employed Women's Association) in Ahmadabad and NASVI (National Alliance for Street Vendors of India) achieved great milestones in conditions of vendors with pressing for issuing identity cards by SEWA to hawkers that act as licenses and banks that lend money specifically to Hawkers. Imphal in Manipur is another city where street hawking is given legal status although some fees are charged by the Corporation for cleaning garbage etc.

Train hawkers that see the government as their only hope must be assured of the few yet major ways that civil society can help to better their conditions. The Media that is given high regard by society must be used to voice the unheard voices looking at train

hawkers not as collectives or categories like Hawkers, Beggars etc. but as persons deprived of their needs and rights.

Train hawkers are a person's striving for economic self reliance hence we must see them as contributors to a new India, as business people. Train Hawkers are part of the world of commerce and communally must find a place in the chambers of commerce to contribute further to the country's economy. People could patronize their goods without being paternalistic to encourage these budding entrepreneurs'. Besides the civil society could campaign in the interest of hawkers that government make efforts to integrate them in urban plans, to campaign for an environment which promotes and strengthens this sector and works towards the ultimate goal of employment and sufficient work for all.

References:

- Fredrick Schneider, Colin Williams. (2013). *The Shadow Economy*. The Institute of Economic affairs, Great Britain.
- Informal/Unorganized sector. Online available on: <http://www.doccentre.org/docsweb/urban-issues/hawkers/BCPT-hawkers-1stpage.htm>
- Interview of Ella R.Bhatt the 'founder' of the Self-Employed Women's Association (SEWA) Key concerns and policies on Hawkers. Online available on: <http://www.india-seminar.com/2000/491/491%20interview.htm>
- Jumani Usha, Joshi Bharati. (1882). *Legal Status of Hawkers in India, Self Employed Women's Association Ahmedabad*, Pg44, Pg56.
- Kabra Kamal. Akram. (2003). 'The Unorganised Sector in India: Some Issues Bearing on the Search for Alternatives.' *Social Scientist*, Vol. 31, No. 11/12 (Nov. - Dec., 2003), pp. 23-46. Online available on: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3517948>.
- National Commission for enterprises in the unorganised sector (2007) *Report on conditions of work and Promotion of Livelihoods in the Unorganized Sector*, Pg 64-67 and Pg 17-Petty Trade in India: *Street Vendors/Hawkers*, New Delhi. Online available on: http://dcmsme.gov.in/Condition_of_workers_sep_2007.pdf
- *Portes Alejandro, Haller William. (2005). The Informal Economy, Princeton University Press, New Jersey.*
- Report of the National Commission on Labour (1966-69), Chapter (vii)-The Unorganized Sector. New Delhi.
- Sharit Bhowmik. (2007). *Hawkers in the Urban Informal Sector: A study of street vendors in six cities*, National Alliance of Street Vendors of India. Online available on: <http://wiego.org/sites/wiego.org/files/publications/files/Bhowmik-Hawkers-URBAN-INFORMAL-SECTOR.pdf>
- Soto De Hernando. (1989). *The Other Path*, Hawper and Row publication, New York.
- The Bombay Municipal Corporation Act. (1882). *Introduction3-Pg19*. Online available on: <http://mumbaisuburban.gov.in/borivali/pdf/mmc.pdf>
- November 23, (1993) *Suburban railways, The supermarket on wheels*, Indian Express.
- November 10, (2005) *Mumbai crush: 4,700 jam train for 1, 700*, The Asian Age.
- Personal Correspondence
- Mr. Pravesh Gupta (Train Hawker on Central Railway), Mr.Hari Ram Yadav (Secretary of the Mumbai Hawkers Union), Mr. Shankar Salvi (President of Mumbai Hawkers Union), Mr. Ansari (In-charge of Amchi Kholi, Day Recreational Centre for Street Children), Sharit K. Bhowmik, Department of Sociology, Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai.
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RESEARCH ESSAY ON WOMEN'S RIGHTS AND LITERATURE

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(Regd: **01IWRA2016**)

Abstracts:

It may sound funny to you but my paper starts with a joke—which is the most dangerous alphabet?—it is a tension generator...because all the worries start with “W”...Who? Why? What? When? Which? Whom? Where? War...Wine...Whisky...Wealth...Women...and finally...WIFE!

A good laugh, which is what, was expected of you. But have we ever thought that this laugh has turned the plight of half of the population into a miserable, beastly joke, a joke that arouse nothing but disgust and fear and so long it does not happen with one of our family members a sense of gratitude for the God almighty—thank God—we are spared.

Aren't we women and human too? Can't we marry the person of our choice, can't we opt the field in which we can explore our genius, can't we have a little fun in our life, and don't we have the right even on our womb so that we can birth our little daughters? Or, is the crime so great that the punishment meted out to us is beyond any human or beastly territory. Perhaps I am wrong, when I talk about beasts or beastly crime. In animal kingdom no she-animal is raped by a flock of animals for choosing a mate outside her clan, or acid-attacked for not complying the love proposal of a he-animal. What a great relief! At least animals do not infect themselves with the behavior of the 'noble savage'.

The aim and objective of my paper is to show that apart from rules and laws another most potent tool to establish human rights in society is literature. For, it is literature which reveals myriad forms of lives and a deep understanding and respect for them as well.

The methodology of the paper will be based on the analysis of some of the Indian and African-American literary texts.

Keywords: Fiction, Identity, Human Rights, Respect, Literature, Woman Rights etc.

Human Rights originate from the self-respect and significance of human being. Human rights are inherently available to all human beings. They are natural in a human person. But they are recognized and protected by the legal systems of all the civilized states. They are the result of harsh experience of the Second World War that led to all nations to agree to an international uniform norm of human rights.¹ After the Second World War, they accepted the importance and worth of human beings and they became the subject of the International law. They did not meet any difficulty in achieving harmony for preparing the universal norms of universal application. The notion of equality and non-discrimination on the ground of gender finds its place in all international instruments dealing with human rights.² Women who comprise half of humanity are frequently subjected to mistreatment and violations of human rights. The International Instruments direct an obligation on the member States to integrate provisions for the elimination of sex prejudiced and discriminatory laws and practices and for granting equivalent rights to women with those of men. All differences, limitations and prohibition which are present traditionally, impairs the true enjoyment by women and implementation of rights of women by states. The documents have initiated to provide fundamental freedoms by the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, 1979. It also required the Member States to take steps to

eliminate all customs, traditions and sacred practices that discriminate against women.³

'Swayamsiddha' we are not. No human being can be. And how to make you believe in the concept of 'Ardhnaarieshwar' we have failed to. Does it hurt someone so much if someone who happens to be a woman, wants to live like a human being? Or, was the crime of Eve (to taste the forbidden fruit) so great that all the coming generations of her daughters will have to pay ad infinitum? An overwhelming question it sounds. But the solution is so simple. Live and let live. I am not a feminist who believes in equality. But a humanist I am with staunch faith in humanity and dignity of life in any form.

Before presenting my paper to you I would like to read out for you a piece of paper that might have crossed your vision but then I hope your kindness will allow me to repeat and in doing so, my only objective is to know from this eminent audience that what is the message we are getting from this article by a very eminent columnist. (Chetan)

For me human right means access to such an atmosphere where one can explore one's maximum potentiality irrespective of differences whether of biology, caste, class, or creed. To reflect my point-of-view I have explored some of the literary texts and have done a close textual analysis. The first text is Toni Morrison's *Sula* and the second one is Anita Nayar's *Ladies Coupe*. The first one is an African-American fiction and the second one is a penned by a well known Indian author. Both are women-centric and deals with women characters who do not conform to the social prescription laid down by the male

¹ Roland Burke, Decolonization and the Evolution of International Human Rights, University of Pennsylvania Press, 2010. P. 264

² Tenzin Gyatso, H.H. the XIVth Dalai Lama, Human Rights, Democracy and Freedom available at <http://www.dalailama.com/messages/world-peace/human-rights-democracy-and-freedom> accessed on 28th February 2016

³ <http://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/cedaw/> accessed on 14th February 2016

society. They live impermissibly however painful it may be.

I always thought of Sula as quintessentially black, metaphysically black, if you will, which is not melanin and certainly not unquestioning fidelity to the tribe. She is new world black and new world woman extracting choice from no-choice, responding inventively to found things. Improvisational. Daring, disruptive, imaginative, modern, out-of-the-house, outlawed, unpolicing, uncontained and uncontainable. And dangerously female (Toni Morrison, *Unspeaking Things Unspoken* 1-34).

This is what, in the words of Toni Morrison, Sula is for us. She is the 'dangerously female' protagonist of Morrison's second novel *Sula* that was published in 1973. Like her first novel *The Bluest Eye* the focus in this novel is on women but in different context. Lyrical and gripping, it is an honest look at the power of friendship amid a background of family, race, love, gender and the human condition.

Toni Morrison's first novel *The Bluest Eye* was acclaimed as the work of an important talent written... as John Leonard said in the New York Times...in a prose "so precise, so faithful to speech and so charged with pain and wonder that the novel becomes poetry." Her second novel *Sula* has the same power, same beauty. The novel spells out the story of two women-friends since childhood, separated in young adulthood, and reunited as grown up women. Nel Wright grows up to become a wife and mother, happy to remain in her hometown of Medallion, Ohio. She conforms to the role society has assigned to a woman. On the other hand Sula Peace leaves Medallion to experience college, men and life in the big city, an exceptional choice for a black woman to make in the late 1920s. But Sula makes this exceptional choice to get out

of the Bottom, the hilltop neighborhood where "beneath the sporting life of the men hanging around the place in head rags and soft felt hats there hides a fierce resentment of failed crops, lost jobs, thieving insurance men, bug ridden flour...at the invisible life that cannot be overstepped... (where)...the laughter was part of the pain". [Morrison, *Sula*, 4).

Sula fails to inhabit the social place that has been forged for her, or for that matter a female. She is being introduced for us in appropriately strained manner for her reappearance in the neighborhood is full of foreboding. Armed with a college education and an edgy cynicism, Sula is an outcast from the start. Her status as a woman without a man and a woman without children simply does not translate into a life that the Bottom understands. Sula's grandmother, Eva, speaks for the whole community when she tells her granddaughter to have some babies, that it will "settle" her. When Sula responds defensively, they argue:

"I don't want to make somebody else. I want to make myself."
"Selfish. Ain't no woman got no business floatin' around."
"Without no man."
"You did".
"Not by choice".
"Mama did".
"Not by choice, I said. It ain't right for you to want to stay off by yourself"(92).

Eva (like Eve, the first woman) has been the reigning matriarch of her own family/community for years and she is powerful and independent and fierce in the role. Even though she is not part of a couple herself, to simply reject the notion out-of-hand is incomprehensible, even to her. It is accepted template for women's lives, even though it is, more often than not a failed or malfunctioning model. Furthermore, to Eva and to people in

the Bottom children is part of the order of the things, the literal outgrowth of a concept of a womanhood that is valued by what it produces and tends. To Sula, however, being a wife and a mother are not pre-requisites for selfhood. Her own "business"...the business of being, of living...is not dictated by family or community. She simply does not accept gender stereotypes or roles. And this questioning attitude or rather challenge exasperates her community.

From the vantage point of the Bottom, the adult Sula thwarts community's mores surrounding gender, race and vocation / avocation, generating a tension that is three-fold. Her disinterest is interpreted as selfishness; she believes in self-nurture as an end in and of itself, whereas for Eva, Nel and other women in toe, mothering, care-taking and running a household are non-negotiable women's work. And third, she is not ready to exchange her selfhood for any of the prescribed social-security, a norm which no Eve, black or white, is allowed to break. She wants to have her own rights to live, which is nothing but evil to be cured.

The question that can a woman survive alone is the pivot of the novel *Ladies Coupe* by Anita Nair. It is a fiction that spells out the facts of a woman's or rather women's life regardless of their geographical, cultural, religious, social or economical differences. Whatever they are or whoever they are they share one thing in common. And that thing is "affliction" and the first site of this affliction is family itself.

Sula escapes Bottom to evade the prescription of her society, black African society for a woman. The novel *Ladies Coupe* opens with 'a sense of escape' for Akhila, an escape from the inevitability of her life which demands her to do 'what is expected of her'

(Nair, Anita. *Ladies Coupe*, 1). She can dream about the rest if she wishes so. Akhila, the dutiful eldest daughter of the family is not allowed to think of her own. Her dreams and desires always take a back seat when it comes to her family. But the family consisting of her mother, two brothers, and one younger sister never appreciated her sacrifice. "Which is why she collects epithets of hope like children collect ticket stubs? To her, hope is enmeshed with unrequited desires." (1) "So this then is Akhila. Forty-five years old... Sans husband, children, home and family. Dreaming of escape and space. Hungry for life and experience. Aching to connect" (2).

Tragedy at very early stage of her life makes her a pre-mature adult forbidding her to dream young. Akhila's father, the breadwinner of the South Indian Brahmin family meets an accidental death, leaving his family forlorn. Akhila, being the eldest one puts on the yoke on her tender shoulder, becomes an income-tax clerk and looks after the needs of her family. She fulfills all the responsibilities of her family by providing her younger brothers education, getting her younger sister married and even establishing the families of her brothers too. She always play role of a daughter, sister, aunt, provider and but never she is allowed to live her own life, never asked what 'she' wants. Being the earning member and also because the job demanded long hours and tedious journey from home to office Akhila was unable to perform the house-hold chores. She also imagines that will she be able to cope-up alone if needed? The family tries their best to make her believe that a woman cannot survive alone and even if she tries it will be a kind of hell for her. For long she accepted this without any question only rarely being disturbed by this 'Yaksha prasna.'

Another aspect of the fiction, though related to the same question of woman's

individuality is the special ticket counter on Indian railway station that was in existence before the early 1998. Those special counters were meant for senior citizens, women and handicapped. So, this was a kind of leveling of woman along with the two other categories. Not only that, but ladies coupés in most overnights trains with second class reservation were also in practice putting women on the same footage with senior citizens and handicapped. This practice was also trying to give a woman the same message that a single woman cannot take care of herself and like the elderly and handicapped people she needs to be looked after by someone, in this case of course a male. Hence, the journey of single, very much adult Akhila in this all women compartment in search of an answer for her perennial question, 'can a woman without a man be happy and contented?' For all the time she is being admonished by her family 'A woman can't live alone. A woman can't cope alone' (16). She further says that at this juncture of life "marriage is unimportant. Companionship, yes, I would like that. The problem is, I wish to live by myself but everyone tells me that a woman can't live alone. What do you think? Can a woman live by herself?" (21). She finds herself in an enclosure in which she can move round and round without arriving anywhere, or at any conclusion. But as we shall see, it is some of the women who help her to step out of this vicious circle and go ahead in her life.

Akhila boards with this question along with five other women of different age groups and diverse backgrounds to the train for Kanyakumari in search of a viable answer. But meanwhile what she is 'trying to do is convince myself that a woman can live alone' (21). Other travelers in that ladies coupé are Prabha Devi, Janki Devi, Margaret Shanti, Fourteen years old Sheela, and Marikolanthu. Lives of these ladies are lived in diverse

economical, cultural, social environments but somehow or somewhere all have been denied their natural self to grow. In the intimate atmosphere of ladies coupé Akhila listens their stories and shares her own with them. While listening to them she is drawn into the most private moments of their lives, seeking in them a solution to the question that has been with her all her life : can a woman stay single and be happy, or does she need a man to make her complete? When she tossed the question to ladies the wisest answer comes through the character of Margaret Shanti. She says: "You should trust your instincts... You have to find your own answers. No one can help you do that" (21). She is a chemistry teacher who is well aware of the poetry of elements. But she is married to an insensitive tyrant who is too self-absorbed to recognize her needs. Prabha Devi is a perfect daughter and wife who recognize her own worth after having a glimpse of a swimming pool. After learning to swim she was able to 'triumph over her innate timidity and rise above tradition to float' (208). Janki Devi is a pampered wife and a confused mother who leads a very sheltered life. Then there is fourteen year old Sheela who is more mature than her parents and knows the people and their inner urges. Marikolanthu is another character who is not very educated but then she is educated in the school of life. Her life is destroyed by one night of lust of a man. She becomes an unwed, unwilling mother, who bears her life as a kind of use me but do not abuse me attitude. Other women characters whose lives come into dialogue are Karpagam, Sujata Akka, Chettiar Amma etc. It is only Karpagam, Akhila's school friend who asserts herself as a woman without any guilt and it is she who plays the catalyst in Akhila's life, and it is she who prepares Akhila to look for a new dimension in her life. She says to Akhila that I do wear colorful clothes and jewelry though I am a widow. "Would you rather that I dressed in

white and went about looking like a corpse ready for the funeral pyre?" (202). Akhila denies but when she asks that how her family reacts Karpagam says emphatically, "I don't care what my family or anyone thinks. I am who I am. And I have as much right as anyone else to live as I choose...It has nothing to do with whether...her husband is alive or dead. Who made these laws anyway? Some man who couldn't bear the thought that in spite of his death, his wife continued to be attractive..." (202). And "Akhila realized with shame that while she had in the manner of a docile water-buffalo wallowed in a pond of self-pity allowing parasites to feast on her, Karpagam had gone ahead and learnt to survive" (202). This meeting with her friend worked as a catalyst in the life of Akhila as it brought her "out of...the dark and dismal hues of the world she had lived in for so long now." Now she was sure enough to do 'what she intended to do with her life.' What Akhila hated most was not having an identity of her own. "She was always an extension of someone's else's identity...Akhila wished for once someone would see her as a whole being...what Akhila most desired in the world was to be her own person...To do as she pleased. To live as she chose with neither restraint nor fear of censure...she didn't want a husband. Akhila didn't want to be a mere extension again" (200).

Now Akhila defines happiness for Karpagam. She says 'Happiness is being allowed to choose one's own life; to live it the way one wants. Happiness is knowing one is loved and having someone to love. Happiness is being able to hope for tomorrow' (200).

Now Akhila is ready to face the truth when asked by her brother Narayan, 'How will you cope?...How can any woman cope alone?' (206) Akhila had her answer ready. "I know I can. I did once before when you were children. Now I can for me, for Akhilandeswari. Nobody's daughter. Nobody's sister. Nobody's wife. Nobody's mother" (206-7). Akhila wants to be herself; wants to live for her 'own self.' Sula also wanted the same but she was not allowed either by her family or the society and she had to die but Akhila is ready to face another tomorrow without any baggage of expectations, free to explore herself confidently.

To live one's life without disturbing the other's one is the bare minimum one can expect from the society which holds the flag of Human Rights and Human Rights should get translated into Women's Rights as well. For, it will be suicidal for any society to ignore its half of the population to lag behind in search of growth and glory.

References

1. Morrison, Toni, *Unspeakable Things Unspoken: The Afro-American Presence in American Literature*, Michigan Quarterly Review 28 (1989): 1-34.

-----Sula Vintage; Random House. 1973.

2. Nair, Anita. 2001. *Ladies Coupé*. New Delhi: Penguin.

WOMEN EMPOWERMENT AND ACHIEVEMENTS: A PATH TOWARDS TRANSFORMATIVE LEADERSHIP

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Abstracts:

Women have always led a life of oppression and exploitation, being the most ostracized and marginalized sections of the society. But gone are the days when women were subjected to all kinds of injustices and discrimination on the name of sexual harassment, rape, dowry and domestic violence. The times have changed and the facts reveal that today's women are examples of self independent and empowered entities who are well-awakened and conscious of their rights and powers. The paper is an attempt to showcase the journey of women's transformation, signifying women empowerment and achievement. The paper by employing Case Study Method tries to make an indepth study of a leading women organization whose role and functions are the testimonial of how today's women have become courageous and more confident in raising their voice against all social evils and gender injustices and gender biases to grant women their deserved rights and dignified place in the society.

Keywords: achievement, courageous, dignified place, oppression, women empowerment

Wrapped silence, soaring rage, fear of being ostracized and marginalized and the inability to speak out and express in forms and words are perhaps the few definitive terms for a woman's description in India a few years back. Clothed in years of deplorable suffering under the wrap of oppressive practices such as bigamy, dowry, domestic violence and also the various manifested forms of sexual offence, rape, women are really coming out in the open now, at last braving all odds to shed their long standing fears and inhibitions. In the wake of the horrific Delhi gang rape in December 2012, there has been an overhaul of the rape and sentencing laws thereby scrutinizing national gender policy and also sensitizing women as equal citizens and participants and raising several questions related to women safety and gender justice in the present times. Certainly there are changes. There is much more awareness now especially about violence against women manifested in rape, property issues or communal riots. Women are not as invisible in 2014-15. But the greatest problem that remains is the huge gap between promise and implementation. Pay disparity, prevailing prejudices and poor and unequal representation in the total workforce are some of the problems we can't deny working women grapple with. Gender bias and gender

discrimination continues to be an enormous problem within Indian society. India still has a very low ranking in the Gender-Gap Index. There are numerous dominant gender equity issues prevalent in India as the Indian society still continues to be patriarchal.

Well, a Nirbhaya still gets crucified somewhere for buying few moments of her freedom and happiness, a Rohtak girl still meets a savage death crushing all norms of humanity and a housewife still languishes somewhere in the dark corridors of her suffocating silence. Undeniably women have always been and will always be lynched in forms and ways but then as destruction always leads to creation and death to living, women have evolved too. From household to socio-political, business and entrepreneurship, they have really taken to multi-tasking, signifying a great development in the area of women empowerment and gender justice and women's transformative leadership. When it comes to leadership the examples are huge and still roaring.

Closing all gender gaps are aspiring stories of women role models who scaled impossible heights to attain success and leadership. They have left their indelible mark and modern India's script cannot be complete without their contributions. Women are at the forefront of social movements, hold important political positions and have also gone a long way in boosting the corporate sector with their enterprise and skilled and efficient performance. Do you know that we are number 15 in the world when it comes to political empowerment. Women are 25% of the Union Cabinet, 10% of Parliament, 9% of MLA's across India and we've had a woman head of state and head of government. Arundhati Roy became the

first Indian woman to win the Booker Prize for the novel "God of small Things" and instead of embracing glory that came along with it, she took to controversies with her writings, on dams, Maoists and the Kashmir issue. Chanda Kochar the CEO of ICICI Bank (India's biggest private bank) has been listed by the Fortune Magazine as among the top powerful women in business. Ela Bhatt, the Ramon Magsasay Awardee went a long way in becoming a pioneer of self employed women's association (SEWA) with 687,000 women members. SEWA's women members are vegetable and garment vendors, bidli rollers, paper pickers, incense stick makers and also agricultural workers.

Kiran Bedi, a simple girl brought up in both hindu and sikh traditions grew up to become a famous tennis champion, joined IPS, worked at different key positions earning the title of India's first and highest woman ranking officer, also joined as Inspector General of Delhi Prisons and the sole person behind introducing several reforms for the inmates of Tihar Jail. Sushmita Sen, a famous model and the holder of beauty pageant Miss Universe Title, she is the perfect example of women's transformative leadership. From again a very humble childhood to being the recipient of the world's most prestigious beauty and glamour event title, from being a great model to being a single mother, she has truly demonstrated that women are no longer weaker in comparison to men and they have all the skills and potentials to challenge the men and demand for gender justice and gender equality. . Shahnaz Hussain, a role model in the field of beauty and care. She is again a very famous Indian woman entrepreneur who has created a mark for herself in the pages of history

by her herbal cosmetic products under the brand name of Shehnaz. Who can forget the name of Mrs. Aruna Roy? A prominent Indian political and social activist. The pioneer of the great "Mazdoor Kisan Shakti Sangathan", the sole person behind the Right to Information Act. Indra Nooyi, again a befitting example of women's changing perspectives and personality. Being the chairperson & CEO of Pepsi Co, she has consistently ranked among the world's 100 most powerful women. The list is endless with many more names like Shikha Sharma, CEO, Axis Bank, Preetha Reddy, MD Apollo Hospital Enterprises, Shobhana Bhartia, Chairperson HT Media, Vinita Bedi, MD Britannia Industries, Naina Lal Kidwai, Country Head, HSBC India. All these women have shown the world that women are no longer just a body of flesh and bones but they can also be examples of highly confident and courageous people who can play the role of great leaders behind the development and transformation of society and can be role model for the masses.

Well all these examples of women leadership in different areas hint enough that feminist interests and strategies have undergone drastic changes with the unfolding times, perhaps more recently. Besides change in the societal structure, government's initiative towards women empowerment and the change in the thinking pattern of men folk, it was also the result of a change in the ambitions of women which played a major role in the over all development of their personality. Men's systematic control over women's sexuality have undergone a plunge in all institutional wings such as family, community, market and state. Women across the board have really emerged as key players in reproductive activities of

family, community, business, occupation and society. It is also remarkable to see that more women than men tend to be advocates for women's interests both practical and strategic.

1. Review of Literature

Kollan Bharti & Parikh J. Indira in their paper titled, "A Reflection of the Indian Women in Entrepreneurial World", discusses the chief reasons behind women's transformation.

- 1) Women regarded work as an integral aspect of their life space
- 2) Income Generation and a career choice where both the social system and occupation were equally significant
- 3) Educated and qualified women aspired for a different role and life vis-à-vis their stereotyped role as mothers and grandmothers
- 4) The women wanted homes, marriage and children as well as occupation also became a top priority in the lives of few women who wanted to lead a life of independence, self-respect and confidence
- 5) The women accepted the social traditional role behaviors from the older generation but from their husbands, colleagues and children, they expected understanding and support in their occupation choice. They looked for redefinition of systems and redesigned interfaces across the systems and institutions they worked with

According to the Global Gender Gap Report 2013, released by Non-Profit organization, World Economic Forum,

ranked India at 101 among 136 countries that were assessed for women empowerment on social, economic and political parameter. The report ranks countries by measuring the size of the gender inequality gap in four areas

- Economic participation and opportunity
- Health and survival
- Educational attainment
- Political growth empowerment

India is the only South Asian country that has consistently fluctuated a lot in the gender gap rankings since 2009. According to the report “India is ranked 9th in the world in the list of countries where women are most empowered politically, marginally behind its South Asian counterpart Bangladesh, that is ranked 7th. But at rank 135, India is rated the worst in South Asia when it comes to ensuring health and survival for its women and ranked behind Bangladesh and Nepal on the parameter of economic participation and opportunity.

No doubt there are four reasons for the gender gap in India. The double burden of holding down a job while looking after the family, the inability to use the “anytime-anywhere” performance model, the lack of public and societal support mechanisms and the limited number of role models and opportunity. We have cited a lot for gender equality and a radical practical approach to women issues so that every women can feel a leader in her own capacity. For that a change is needed. Just as Prime Minister Narendra Modi has launched the “Swachh Bharat Abhiyaan”, its time he launch a campaign for women employment. For the first time powerful women ministers are there in the cabinet. They should make this an issue rather than focus on

whether IIM or IIT canteens should stick to a vegetarian menu.

As rightly said by Oxfam(Canada), an international organization working worldwide to find solutions to deal with poverty, “ That the kind of changes we want to see in society requires transformative leadership. Gender justice is the goal of full equality and equity among women and girls and men and boys in all spheres of life. It is the result of women jointly- and on an equal basis with men-defining and shaping the policies, structures and decisions that affect their lives and society as a whole. It is both an outcome and a process. Gender Justice requires we work together on two levels.

- a) To change societal attitudes and behavior that lie at the heart of gender inequality
- b) To change those laws, policies and government programmes that discriminate against women and sustain gender inequality”

Kawatra, S. & Krishnan, V.R.(2004), talks about women’s transformational leadership and how the life of women have changed drastically from just being a pound of flesh to occupying positions carrying great leadership roles and responsibilities. In his literature review section, Lord, De Vader and Alliger (1999) have suggested that masculinity-Femininity is an important personality trait in forming leadership perceptions. Rosener (1990) showed that women described themselves in ways that characterize transformational leadership. Eagly and Johannesen Schnidt (2001) meta-analyzed 47 studies and showed that women exceeded men significantly on individualized consideration. A significant study in the direction of showcasing how women have transformed themselves drastically have

been done by Batliwada, S. & Rao, A. (2002). The authors by taking interviews of eighteen outstanding women leaders have uncovered many major facts and issues related to women's transformative leadership, their perspectives and visions. Through conversations, women talked about the practice of women leadership for bringing about social change. The interviewees while supporting women's leadership, pointed out the need for:

- Building an enabling environment for the articulation of women's visions of development and rights at a global level
- Supporting coalition building within the women's movement and across women's organizations as well as coalitions between the women's movement and other social change movements
- Challenging power structures and resource control in the political, economic and social arenas and in all types of organizations that keep women and women's interests out
- Supporting the emergence and sustenance of women leaders at all levels for a transformative social change agenda
- Building accountability mechanisms across institutional arenas for women's interests

2. Objective of Study

The following were the objectives behind the study:

1. To develop a deeper insight by making an exhaustive study of existing literature dealing with the cases highlighting Women Transformation and Women

Empowerment and their achievements..

2. To bring out certain facts related to the issues of Women Empowerment, Achievements, Gender Equality and Gender Justice on the basis of a practical field based Case Study highlighting the immense transformation in the consciousness level of women regarding their rights and powers in the present times which motivates them to fight against all kinds of Gender Injustice and Biases leading towards Women Empowerment.

3. Research Methodology

The study employs Case Study Method to develop a deeper understanding about how women have come in the forefront and have started exercising their fundamental rights and independence to showcase their opinion in front of the masses. The study describes about a real life case study of a leading and well established Women Organization where few courageous and extremely dedicated women members are playing a major role to exhibit their existence as strong identities in the society at par with men, signifying Gender Justice and Women Transformation and Achievements.

As a part of the Case Study Method, Interview was also conducted of the leading members of the organization to collect information on the roles and functions of the body and their achievements as an exemplary women body.

Along with the case study method, Secondary Data has also been used to get an insight about the issue of

Women's Transformative Leadership in the past few years.

4. Case Study

When we talk of women empowerment and their achievements and the journey of women's transformation from a timid, highly tortured and discriminated identity to a strong and awakened identity, we need to go to the grass root level and make a deeper study of those cases where women have truly showed their existence and have become an example of women empowerment and role models for the masses.

As a part of the Research Method, a Case Study was conducted of a leading woman organization based in the region of Virar, a suburban region of Palghar District, Taluka Vasai, Mumbai, Maharashtra. The group is called by the name of "Mahila Dakshata Samiti", a leading woman organization consisting of a committee of few highly dedicated and extremely focused and courageous women who have been fighting and raising their voice against all social odds and evils and gender injustices and biases prevalent in the society

Mahila Dakshata Samiti is a powerful woman organization group and a part of Virar Police Station. The body has been created by the Virar Police Station and has been functioning as a significant part of it serving the purpose of women empowerment and transformation from the past 20 years. The group consists of 15 outstanding women members drawn from the different walks of life and who have voluntarily agreed to dedicate their time and skills for the upliftment of women and granting them justice. This group in association with Virar Police Station works almost 24 hrs , fully dedicated for the purpose of listening to

women's problems and solving them on time.

The names of Committee Members along with their contact numbers are displayed on the board of Virar Police Station and whenever any case related to women injustice and torture comes to the police station, the case is handed over to the Mahila Dakshata Samiti immediately, based on the area of the incident and the availability of the members in the region to resolve the problem. A very significant part of the functioning of the Mahila Dakshata Samiti Committee is that besides the routine police investigations, the committee members also help in going into the depth of the incident , interrogating the aggrieved woman and all concerned parties, finding out the truth of the incident. A noticeable exploration of my study was that the Samiti Members besides their routine investigations, also employ Counseling as a primary method of resolving various cases which come to them.

To make the study more factual and indepth, an interview was also conducted of the two leading members of the Mahila Dakshata Samiti. They are:

1. Mrs. Ashwini Shinde, who had entered into politics at a tender age of 22 yrs. She has been associated as an active member of the Mahila Dakshata Samiti from the past 10-12 yrs. She is a member of the Virar Police Station and a member of the Vikas Aghadi Party, which is a leading party of the Palghar District and the Vasai Taluka region. She has also been very active in politics and had been even nominated for the Corporator post under the Aghadi Party.

2. Mrs. Jyoti Pawar is a very senior member of Virar Mahila Sangathan of Shiv Sena, Virar Region. She is also an outstanding Social Worker and an active politician too. She has been an active member of Shiv Sena from the past 20 years and has been associated with Mahila Dakshata Samiti and Virar Police Station from the past 12 years.

As a part of the interview, a couple of questions were asked related to the nature of functioning of the committee and the varied nature of cases dealt by them which helped immensely in women empowerment.

On being asked as to what is their nature of functioning, the interviewees replied that the names and contact numbers of all the Samiti Committee members is displayed on the board of the Virar Police Station and as soon as a case of women injustice or torture or gender violence or women's rights comes to the police station, the women committee members become instantly active and they are immediately contacted by the police authorities to start their indepth investigations into the case by their interrogations and various other measures which they employ to bring out the truth of the case. The Samiti members are far more successful in revealing the truth of the case as they being women can understand the aggrieved woman party in much more better manner. The woman victim too feels more comfortable to discuss their painful stories and everything related to the incident in detail with no concealment with the women Mahila Dakshata Samiti members and this is the biggest achievement of the functioning. The interviewed women replied that they are on duty almost 24 hrs and are always

vigilant on the issue of women rights and independence. The members start their own pattern of investigations as soon as a case approaches them and their discovery of truth is considered as a significant part of the case and the various facts discovered by the committee members are authenticated by their signatures before the case is presented in the court. Their signatures are given a great amount of weightage in normal police investigations and court proceedings. The police station maintains a register consisting of the details of the case and the summary of the course of action followed by the members of the Mahila Dakshata Samiti to resolve the case.

Another important question was are they paid being a member of the body. The two ladies replied that all women who want to serve for the betterment of women sections and want to fight for women rights and women empowerment, voluntarily become a member of this body and it is not a salaried occupation. Most of the women members of the Mahila Dakshata Samiti besides being members of the body are also into some or the other profession. The two interviewed women had their own Catering Business besides being members of the Samiti.

To find out the varied number of tasks carried out by the body, the ladies were asked about the different functions performed by them, they replied that they deal with all types of cases involving women rights, safety, women atrocities and fighting for their cause.

The following are some of the very important areas they work upon which have tremendously contributed in Women Empowerment and have been a major part of Women Achievement :

1. Counselling the woman victim in terms of suicide cases and trying to

- find out the real reason behind their suicide, making them come out of their miseries and helping them to lead a normal life.
2. Fighting against black marketing and illegal hoarding of goods in ration shops and staging protests for it
 3. Dealing with cases of fraud involving sale of jewellery, where specially old women are cheated.
 4. Raising the status and dignity of women in the society by taking strict action against the call girls who destroy the serenity and lower down the safety of the area by standing on the road at night which has a bad impact on the passer byes and encourages the men to look at all other passing women in the same manner. The Mahila Dakshata Samiti members had been very active in their fight for bringing back normalcy in the areas and actively participate in the removing this social menace.
 5. Taking care of safety of girls at night along with police authorities
 6. Handling cases of women, specially old women being cheated in ATM Outlets while withdrawing money
 7. Dealing with cases of women safety like gold chain snatching at night. The women members are very active and vigilant in the crowded areas at night and they try to catch all such anti-social elements involved in such acts.
 8. Taking care of maintenance of safety in crowded areas by controlling the goons and vandalizing agents.
 9. Counselling rape victims and motivating them to be strong in their lives and encouraging them in all possible ways to come back to their normal lives

They were also asked to cite certain important cases where they played a very

important role in fighting for women's rights and their freedom and independence. The interviewees replied that every day they come across various critical cases which are highly sensitive and which require great amount of sincere efforts and experience in resolving them. In many rape cases besides police panchnama , they also investigated every small and intricate aspect of the case which can have a good amount of impact on the routine police investigations and in many cases they have been successful in revealing significant facts related to the case. They replied that they also had long discussions with the rape victim as they feel more free and comfortable to narrate their painful incident and every such truth related to their case in front of the members of Mahila Dakshata Samiti, as they are women members. The members had also been very successful in resolving one more case involving extra-marital affair of the husband, where the husband had left no stone unturned in proving his wife an insane. The Samiti members went into the depth of the case and investigated the various medical records maintained at different hospitals where she was admitted. The members staged a very forceful battle fighting for the restoration of normal life to the woman and granting justice to her.

5. Conclusion

To bring transformation in the real sense, still there is a need to remove all crucial barriers to equality. Women transformation and empowerment means working on three major issues and areas

- a) First and foremost the women have to be made financially independent to make them more self-independent and self-reliant and less dependent on

male sections of the society. The real socio-economic upliftment of women can come by their active involvement in economic activities and by developing their ability to earn an independent income.

- b) Creating mass consciousness and awareness regarding the empowerment and development in the life of various victimized and abused and weak sections of women through various active government support and initiatives as well as by the efforts of various woman and social activist organizations
- c) Establishment of more women centric organizations like the National Mission for Empowerment of Women which can work solely with the mission to strengthen women and bring about an all round development of their personality

Still the root causes for all the evils faced by the women are:

- Illiteracy is still prevalent in major sections of women
- Economic dependence is there in a good number of females
- Caste restrictions prevent women to enjoy their piece of liberation
- Religious prohibition still hinders women's growth
- Lack of leadership qualities
- Dominant, indifferent and callous attitude of males in the society since the society still today remains to be patriarchal.
- Violence against women still takes place in some or the other form which requires more conscious and immediate strong efforts from the side of law makers, opinion leaders, and voluntary social and activist organizations in order to raise a

mass awareness about the various heinous crimes inflicted on women. The present situation demands more fast stringent laws and its enforcement.

In the long drawn war of the sexes, why should women have to lobby with men for things which are rightfully theirs. A rightful thought and a gentle persuasion is all that is needed. No matter how much we talk of gender justice and gender equality, complete transformation in the life of women towards delivering a constructive leadership role in society demands great change in the existing power structure and working consistently towards a target of creating a world where men are equal to women in all aspects. Gender gap in politics, in economic participation, in education and in healthcare has to be bridged in. Safety and security at the workplace needs to be heightened and responsibility of motherhood has to be realized and shared. Do you know women in India on average spend 351.9 minutes everyday doing housework while men spend just 51.8 minutes on such duties, a difference of 300.1 minutes. Quite appalling!!! . No doubt the celebration of Women's Day every year indicates a remarkable change in the role and functions of women, in their changing status in society and they emerging as a more strong and confident entities. Every year's Women's Day celebration is again a day dedicated to the demonstration of emerging "Women Power" and their strong determination to fight against all Gender Injustice and Gender Inequality. But inspite of all these facts and initiatives, a lot more still needs to be done to attain the goal of complete Gender Justice and Equality and to bring a major transformation in the lives of women towards their empowerment .

Several legislative enactments and constitutional provisions exist which were solely formulated to provide gender equality and justice to women but the irony of the situation is that inspite of many transformations in the lives of women which have some where led to women occupying key leadership positions, a lot more still requires to be done.

of women and men. *Journal of Social Issues*, 57, 781-797.

- Batliwada, S. & Rao, A. (2002). Conversations with Women on Leadership and Social Transformation. *Gender at Work*, 1-33

Reference

- Bharti, K. & Indira, P. J. (2005). A Reflection of the Indian Women in Entrepreneurial World. *Research and Publications, Indian Institute of Management, Ahmedabad*, 1-15
- Global Gender Gap Report. (2013). Released by Non-Profit organization, World Economic Forum. Retrived from:
www.jagranjosh.com/.../global-gender-gap-report-2013-india-ranked-at-
- Oxfam, Canada, Gender Justice:TRANSFORMATIVE LEADERSHIP, Retrived from www.oxfam.ca/sites/default/files/mce/ec-transformative-leadership.pdf
- Kawatra, S. & Krishnan, V.R. (2004). Impact of Gender and Transformational Leadership on Organizational Culture. *NMIMS Management Review*, Vol 16 No 1 & 2, pp. 1-6.
- Rosener, J.B. (1990). Ways women lead. *Harvard Business Review*, 68, 119-125.
- Eagly, A. H., & Johannesen-Schmidt, M. C. (2001). The leadership styles

HUMAN RIGHTS OF WOMEN IN 21ST CENTURY- AN OVERVIEW

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Abstracts:

Women equally possess certain birth rights as human rights equal to men. They are eligible to enjoy basic, minimum fundamental rights. They are equally capable and competent with that of men in every field of day to day activities. But due to social, economic, political and cultural disparities and dilemmas, it has become very impossible to woman to live freely in this 21st globalised century. Women are still victims of violations at home, society, and state, national and international level. Therefore, this paper will analyze the impact and implementation of legislations vis-à-vis women at national and international perspective. It will also provide suggestions for better enjoyment of human rights of women.

Keywords: *women, victims, dilemmas, implementation, enjoyment*

Human Rights originate from the self-respect and significance of human being. Human rights are inherently available to all human beings. They are natural in a human person. But they are recognized and protected by the legal systems of all the civilized states. They are the result of harsh experience of the Second World War that led to all nations to agree to an international uniform norm of human rights.¹ After the Second World War, they accepted the importance and worth of human beings and they became the subject of the International law. They did not meet any difficulty in achieving harmony for preparing the universal norms of universal application. The notion of equality and non-discrimination on the ground of gender finds its place in all international instruments

dealing with human rights.² Women who comprise half of humanity are frequently subjected to mistreatment and violations of human rights. The International Instruments direct an obligation on the member States to integrate provisions for the elimination of sex prejudiced and discriminatory laws and practices and for granting equivalent rights to women with those of men. All differences, limitations and prohibition which are present traditionally, impairs the true enjoyment by women and implementation of rights of women by states. The documents have initiated to provide fundamental freedoms by the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, 1979. It also required the Member States to

¹ **Roland Burke**, *Decolonization and the Evolution of International Human Rights*, University of Pennsylvania Press, 2010. P. 264

² Tenzin Gyatso, H.H. the XIVth Dalai Lama, *Human Rights, Democracy and Freedom* available at <http://www.dalailama.com/messages/world-peace/human-rights-democracy-and-freedom> accessed on 28th February 2016

take steps to eliminate all customs, traditions and sacred practices that discriminate against women.³

In 1993, the landmark, World Conference on Human Rights declared Vienna Declaration and Programme adopted by the states: "Human rights of women and girl child are inalienable, integral and indivisible part of the universal human rights." The programme also focused on the equal and full participation of women in all aspects of public life. At international level, other than this, there numerous international documents vis-à-vis the rights of women adopted by United Nations. One of the main purposes of the United Nation was the realization of global co-operation in promoting and protecting the respect for human rights and essential freedoms for all without distinction as to race, sex, language or religion including that of women. Since the beginning, United Nations had concerned of the enjoyment of equal rights by men and woman.⁴ Human Rights and fundamental freedoms are accessible to all persons without distinction as to sex.' The United Nations Charter requires the United Nations not to place any restrictions on the eligibility of men and women to participate in any capacity in any of its organs.' The recognition and understanding of human rights and the rights of women were considered as one of the procedures of achieving co-operation and unity with the nations. The charter of the United Nations is dedicated to the promotion and achievement of human rights and unless

these rights and freedoms are guaranteed to all men and women without any distinction as to race, caste, language or religion, there cannot have tranquility or security.

Therefore, it is a duty of every state as well as individual to promote and protect of rights of women. They are entitled to guarantee the equal enjoyment and protection of all human rights and fundamental freedoms that include among others:⁵

- The right to life;
- The right to equality;
- The right to liberty and security of person;
- The right to equal protection under the law;
- The right to be free from all forms of discrimination;
- The right to the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health;
- The right to just and favourable conditions of work;
- The right not to be subjected to torture, or other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.

The Constitution of India provides to every citizen of India equality of status and of opportunity as well as justice in the form of social, economic and political. Inequality on the ground of sex has been eliminated and women belonging to diverse religions and races have the same status before the law.⁶ Law is accessible only to those who look for

³ <http://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/cedaw/> accessed on 14th February 2016

⁴ Jose Ayala Lasso, Human Rights In The United Nations: The Achievements So Far And Challenges Ahead, UN High Commissioner for Human Rights, IJPS

⁵ <http://www.drustvo-sos.si/violence-against-women> accessed on 16th February 2016

⁶ Comparative study of anti-discrimination and equality laws of the US, Canada, South Africa and India, http://ec.europa.eu/justice/discrimination/files/comparative_study_ad_equality_laws_of_us_canada_sa_india_en.pdf accessed on 20th February 2016

it, and even to those who seek it, law is sometimes unsighted. Often law is not faithful to the realities of life; it rather follows the logic of proofs. In India, there are number violations against women takes places because they still prefer not to seek the law for lack of awareness, lack of accessibility, lack of financial capacity, lack of seriousness by government machinery, etc. The laws have been, despite of several obstacles, being adopted by parliament to curb dilemma against the Indian women. But in many respects, it is almost totally incapable to alter the social reality, the purpose for which they were created. This social reality is a complex set-up of acutely ingrained beliefs and customs evident in various slights and evident aspects of rural life in this vast country. The law is inaccessible to these areas and to people who necessitate them most. Protective discrimination in favour of women is too insignificant in India. However, as per national familiarity in India, this was one of the most successful experiments that covered the social change in favour of the scheduled castes and tribes. But there are certain contradictory views as well in relation with protective discrimination of women. It led to research based upon scientific, ideological and intellectual forms. The most recent burning issue of women's rights was of reservation bill of women in parliament. Other than that there are number violence's that is faced by women in their day to day activities. In the social activities, there are violations in realtion with health, welfare faced by women. The violations against women results into physical, sexual or psychological destruction or suffering to women.

In the 21st century, women are still fighting for the issues like marital rape, sexual abuse, sexual harassment at work, trafficking in

women and girls with purpose of sexual and other forms of exploitation, forced prostitution, abortion of female foetuses and infanticide of baby girls, traditional practices harmful to women such as genital mutilation, forced or too early marriage, widow burning, honour killing, acid attacks, stoning, war rape, and other. Apartfrom this, cultural patterns, especially in harmful influences of particular traditional practices or customs, education systems, religious beliefs adds more hindrance to life of women.⁷

Therefore, the recognition of human rights is not only sufficient but the effective protection of those rights shall be required by strict laws and its implementation. It is also an essential to to discharge of duties to protect and promote rights of women by United Nations, municipal governments, the police, employers of private and public institutions, families, friends. It is also important to create awareness for and maintain for human rights of women. Therefore, there are certain suggestions listed below :⁸

1. It is important to work more effectively towards Implementation of legislations and policy to eliminate all forms of discrimination against women and to provide equal opportunities.
2. It is necessary to ensure suitable actions to repress all forms of trafficking of women and operation of prostitution of women.
3. In this era, the state shall deliver suitable reservations policies with

⁷ <http://www.drustvo-sos.si/violence-against-women> accessed on 20th February 2016

⁸ http://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/csw/csw53/statements_missions/Fida.pdf accessed on 20th February 2016

- equal opportunities as men in various possible fields.
4. Government should grant that women have the similar rights as men and regarding the nationality of their children.
 5. Government shall take measure to make sure that women have the equal opportunities in all perspectives of an education and training.
 6. Government can take measures to eliminate discrimination in employment so as to ensure that women have the equal right to work, the equal right to the same training and employment opportunities as men and the right to receive equal pay for work of equal value.
 7. Government should take all appropriate measures to eliminate discrimination against women in the field of health care to ensure women and men have equal access to health services including family planning and provide appropriate health services in relation to pregnancy and to grant free services where necessary.
 8. Government should ensure that women have equal access to family benefits, forms of financial credit, including bank loans and mortgages, and the same rights as men to participate in recreational activities, sports and cultural life.
 9. Government should take all appropriate measures to ensure that the particular needs of rural women are met and to ensure rural women have access to health care services, training and employment opportunities, and social security schemes.

To summarize the human rights of women in 21st century, it can be said that, they possess certain birth rights but it is also essential to cherish and enforce them. They could possess, purchase, sell property, engage in trade, donate and inherit property, bring lawsuits and could do so without the help of a man. Other than, they are equally entitled to work, education, protection from sexual abuses, protection from violence's against domestic violence, contradictions & lacunae with respect to some aspects of the law. for development of any society, it is equally important to sustain the rights and interests of all women.⁹

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<http://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Publications/training9chapter13en.pdf> accessed on 21st February 2016

Women Empowerment through Employment Opportunity in INDIA

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Abstracts:

Women empowerment refers to increasing the economic, political, social, educational or spiritual strength of an entity or entities. Women employment is the key and the most essential element which directly influences a woman's empowerment. Employment gives the girl's confidence and her status as financial contributor gets a say in the family and her decision is valued giving her more sense of freedom. Objective of this paper – To portray the demographic employment profile of the women, To study their educational background in relation to their economic opportunities. It is a case study research . Findings in this paper Education and employment are the two basic tools which can change the economic and social status of female in the near future as well as over a long time. Further women empowerment is the utmost requirement for the inclusive growth and development of a nation like India.

Keyword: *women employment, women empowerment, economic opportunity*

Women status in India previously is not better women are dominance in all sphere of her life in the different age like Brahmin age, epic and sutras age etc .The women are totally restricted for widow remarriage free choice marriage girls education etc, women are alive under the four walls of home dowry , purdah system rape cases gender discrimination etc are be more violent on this period but at slowly women of India stepped forward to carry on the movement for independence Women like Aruna Asaf Ali, Sucheta Kriplani and and Usha Mehta and so many freedom fighters like mahatma Gandhi swami Vivekananda, ishwar Chandra Vidya Sagar ,etc are worked for women empowerment during this period. It was during the Quit India movement that Indira Gandhi became actively involved in the freedom struggle. Then the rights is given women not only in one

ground women are independent in socially educationally economically health etc but in all sphere of women are empowered . In Indian constitution of India given priorities for women rights for rights to education rights to work and so many rights for women empowerment out of them one is the economic rights given priorities for women to freely choose her occupation looking to their eligibility and going on this way for her better life and for her better future generations .women empowerment refers to increasing the economic, political, social, educational or spiritual strength of an entity or entities. Women employment is the key and the most essential element which directly influences a woman's empowerment.

Women's economic empowerment – that is, their capacity to bring about economic change for themselves – is increasingly viewed as the most important contributing

factor to achieving equality between women and men. Indian women are almost 50% of the Indian population and they directly as well as indirectly contribute to the economic parameters of the nation. It has been observed that females are more involved into small scale business activities as entrepreneurs but with time change has been noticed and they are moving towards IT/ITES, Apparel/accessories and Food & Beverages. Also traditionally wage employment was noticed in agricultural sector but now service and industrial sectors are witnessing the growth of female workers. In the present social and economic environment women are not treated on equal parameters with the males regarding issues like having authority in the family, property rights, employment opportunities, social and security aspects. Females face different kinds of exploitation in Indian economy and the panacea to all female exploitation is women empowerment in terms of financial status. A strong patriarchal society with deep-rooted socio-culture values continues to affect gender equity and women's empowerment. With time Indian women have evolved under the British rule as well as in the independent economy due to various cultural and economic exposures. Now they participate fully in areas such as education, sports, politics, media, art and culture, service sectors, science and technology, etc. Empowering women also leads to the economic growth, providing employment opportunities, rise in per capita income, poverty reduction rate, socio-economic development and status of women in political participation etc. In India, the constitution has framed to provide the fundamental rights for women regarding equality, social justice and protection against violence. Still there is an existence of discrimination and

inequalities in various sectors of the country. The present study conducted with a purpose to the women empowerment through employment opportunities in India. Not only formal education but also vocational education, self-motivation, self-interest is one of the important key for raising the status of women in economic as well as in others field. Working women in the contemporary society are increasing day by day particularly in the urban setting due to the impact of education, employment opportunities, women reservation policies so forth to mention a few. Indian families are undergoing rapid changes due to the increased pace of urbanization and modernization.

WOMEN ECONOMIC RIGHTS IN RELATE TO HUMAN RIGHTS

After independence the status of women has changed. The political and cultural changes and independence of the country provided equal opportunities to women in education, employment and political participation by which the extent of exploitation of women came down. The year 1975 was declared as the year of International Women's Year, every year 8 March celebrating the international women's day. The Indian Constitution refers to the right to work under the "directive principles of state policy". Article 39 urges the State to ensure that "the citizens, men and women equally, have the right to an adequate means to livelihood".

ROLE OF THE GOVERNMENT /NGO FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT:

The government of India has taken so many steps for providing equal status for women against men. Government is trying

to strengthen women from different dimensions women empowerment include- social empowerment, economic empowerment and gender justice. The government has been implementing various schemes for the socio- economic development. After independence the government launches some article , laws , policy programmes for raising the status of the women .

Further the government has come up with many schemes from time to time to educate females. To name a few: Mahila Samakhya Programme, Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya Scheme (KGBV), and National Programme for Education of Girls at Elementary Level (NPEGEL). Also a Nirbhaya scheme was started in the union budget in 2013 to support initiatives by the government and NGOs working towards protecting the dignity and ensuring safety of women in India. Access to finance Financial development is an important way to empower the poor and women, and to improve their ability to take advantage of economic opportunities. The development of pensions and savings in bank accounts enhance women's ability to make independent decisions on resource use Self-help-groups (microcredit) with 31 million members, of which 80-90% are women. The Bharatiya Mahila Bank (BMB) for women was opened on November 2013 with a vision of economic Guarantee schemes like TRADE in the Ministry for Small and Medium Enterprises give 30% financing of the cost of approved female projects to NGO lending agencies and grants for training Skills-development programs can also make a difference.

OBJECTIVE –

- (1) -To portray the demographic employment profile of the women.
- (2) - To study their educational background in relation to their economic opportunities.

METHODOLOGY

It is a case study research 5 economically empowerment women have taken from Sambalpur motijharan area, married women age between 30-50 yrs .

DESCRIPTION OF THE CASE STUDY

- Parvati oram is a women she is belonging from OBC caste she was completed her education upto 10th standard she got married at 8 yrs ago but unfortunately their husband was die after 5 yrs of her marriage . At that time she was alone with her two daughter and their mother in laws nobody male person in their family for earn some money this time is very difficult to survive and taking care of her two daughter at that time she was going for labour work and 2/3 yrs she work in labour force but she not satisfied in her work and now she has giving a fast food shop and she earn every month 10-15 thousand . she is very happy for their work and family life they prove that through employment they changing her life very well as the time of discussion she told as women education is very important because if she is educated than she taking decision very well and stand up in her life in a difficult situation as well as employment is very important for better survive a peaceful life .

- Zeenat parveen is a muslim women live in Sambalpur , she is belonging from middle income group family she is completing her education up to 12th classes . she living in a 12th yrs marriage relationship , Their husband work in a factories but in demanding society their husband salary is not sufficient for survive as a happy life as well as fullfill their childrens dream, so she is also engage in a cloth business to support her husband. she started her business 5 yrs ago no any problem can be around from their in laws ,family, society, etc . Everybody impression is good for their . After she getting employment their standard of living is change now they better care taker in her family and also their children studied well compare to previous . During the time of discussion she told me employment is very very needed for each and every women because if a women are earning money she is independent than nobody can humiliated because she is powerful in economic wise and also women manage well of her family compare to a male person , in education also “ if women are educated than she is not single in any field and through education as needed she engage in any a type of work and better survive in her life” . “As women empowerment education and employment are two basic tool she told me Today world is the world of education without education a man would be living like a animal and definitely in modern world education is an important element for women empowerment , because if women are educated then their whole family and society are educated” .
- Afreen jahan is a Muslim women lives in a Sambalpur district . she is belonging from middle income group

family, she completed her education upto 12th class she is staying alone with her two children one is 15 yrs daughter and another is 10 yrs boy . she got married before 12 yrs ago after her marriage 6 yrs their husband take drink and beating them in every day . she is well educated compare to her husband they see all those thing and one day she decided to separated from her husband, and finally she along with her two children separated from their husband and now they lives alone in her mother home .for their children bright future and living a happy life she separated from her husband compare to their previous life style from present is too better because she is self independent and better taking care from her 2 children she giving a beauty parlour shop and she earn money in every month around 17000 and she saving money in yearly 28,000. I am asking a question for importance of education and she reply me “ yes education is very important Because if a women are educated then she is not single in any field and through education as needed she engage in any type of work and better survive in her life” and where as their view an employment “in our Indian culture if women are not economically empowered and she is dependent in her husband then her husband any time torture their so if women are economically empowered then any situation she can separated and raising their voice “.their view as for women empowerment importance of education : “ if women are educated then she is knowing all of this for example me i am educated then i am separated from my husband at that time i am giving a beauty parlour shop and managed my family very well i thought that if

women are educated then she is taking decision very well and co- operate self any her family society and for women empowerment” .

- Shama parween is a muslim women lives in Sambalpur she is 50 yrs old belonging from middle income group family, she was got married 17 yrs ago but unfourtunately their husband was die after 13 yrs of her marriage . Now she is staying alone with her 2 daughter , after her husband was die at that time their children was small and all family responsibilities is dependent in their shoulder no any body can financially supporting them . so she was educated and looking to their qualification and interest she joined in a Aaganbadi center as a teacher and started her life . After she get economic support then she better taking care of her 2 daughter, their education , marriage, and making her own home now she is very happy and better survive her life independtly .she told as “better economic condition of women is very important : because money is needed in every stages of life through women are economically empowered then she is raises your voice in any wrong situation and fulfil her own desire” .As their view in importance of women education “ Because if women are educated then she is not single in any field and through education as needed she engage in any type of work and better survive her own life”, their view in women economic empowerment she told as” yes women economically independent is very important and through economically support she better taking care of her family and she cannot depended to other and their little contribution of economic as well

as help for the development of women economic and for the development of the nation”.

- Sony khatoon is a muslim women lives in Sambalpur ,she is belonging from middle income group family, she was completed her education upto 10th class , she got married in 18 yrs ago their marriage life is not happy , because their husband was drinker and all of money he spending her drink after that she see all those thing and joined in a ASHA worker at 5 yrs ago , only for the bright future in her children and so on . Their standard of living is very bad at that time they not joined a work but after she get a job they better survive her life compare to before she told as economic support is very very needed for survive a happy and peace life as their view for women economic rights off course if only men are earning money our economic status is good but if women also earning money then its very good to surviving a better life . And for women empowerment economic is a main path for her development if women earning money then she is understood for her home etc and she is better managing her home as compare to a men . For women education their view as : “ because if women are empowered definitely their future generation is also empowered and education as a main way for women empowered only women are educated not their future well but she is also independent “. where as for women empowerment importance of education “ yes if a women are educated than she is better managing her life example me i am educated but at that time my husband was created violence at home than many problem around in my home for

my me and my children but i stand and taking a good step i am join a government hospital for Asha worker and i help society as well as my home so education is prove me “. she say about women economic empowerment “because in our Indian culture if women are not economically empowered and she is dependent in her husband then her husband any time torture their so if women are economically empowered then any situation she can separated and raising their voice” .

FINDINGS

- From overall research_ its concluded that women are more empowerment in the 21st century and freely participate in economic field . As compare to the vedic age , Brahmans age , sutras and epics age , most of the women are going to economic field and enjoy her economic rights .
- Education both formal and informal is important to achieve women empowerment .
- Employment is important for women empowerment.
- But still as a till date women is also discriminate in many place in class, religion, sex etc , women violence (dowry death, domestic violence sexual harassment in workplace or in other sector female foeticide) in india gender in equalities is also found , beside this is one of the important things is literacy rate of female is very low in many state they are not fully enjoy her rights .

CONCLUSION:

Women’s economic empowerment sets a direct path towards gender equality, poverty eradication and inclusive economic growth. Women make enormous contributions to economics, whether in businesses, on farms, as entrepreneurs or employees, or by doing unpaid care work at home. But they also remain disproportionately affected by poverty, discrimination and exploitation. women perform the bulk of household work, they often have little time left to pursue economic opportunities. It is important to learn about participation of males & females in economy, so that corrective decision may be taken for overall economic growth of the nation. This will require training and skill up gradation in emerging trades, encouraging more women to take up vocational training and employment in the boom sectors. Several researchers have explicit strategies for supporting women's ability to protect their individual and collective women interests at the household, community and macro-levels in india. economically empowering women is a win-win that can benefit not only women, but society more broadly. It promotes women’s ability to achieve their rights and well-being while also reducing household poverty, increasing economic growth and productivity, and increasing efficiency .women’s economic participation and empowerment are fundamental to strengthening women’s rights and enabling women to have control over their lives and exert influence in society. Employment the constitution not only grants equality to women, but also empowers the state to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favour of women. it underscores girl rights, health, women education, gender equality, decision making, poverty eradication and

violence against women. women's reservation bill, which promises 33% of lok sabha seats reserved for women, is put on hold. it would be worthy to conclude with the famous speech of swami vivekananda—”there is no chance of the welfare of the world unless the condition of women is improved. it is not possible for a bird to fly on one wing.”

RECOMMENDATION

- Given priorities to the girls child education as compare to boys for their rights as well as for the better growth and development of a nations like India
- Govt launches various programmes for women empowerment and employment rights but all programmes are not implement properly so better emphasize to all programmes .
- In employment sector should be save and free environment for working women .
- A non working women also give support and training for vocational education and expertise for engage in income generating activities for success her life society and nations .
- After completing her education looking to their eligibility job should be offers .
- Given Counselling and training for rural as well as urban areas of women .
- Womens related Act, law and policy, programmes are should be strictly implemented.

REFERENCE

- *international journal of management and international business studies. issn 2277-3177 volume 4, number 1 (2014), pp. 93-100 © research india publications <http://www.ripublication.com>
- *women empowerment through employment opportunities in india, manisha raj amity university
- *iosr journal of business and management (iosr-jbm) e-issn: 2278-487x, p-issn: 2319-7668. volume 17, issue 4.ver. i (apr. 2015), pp 13-19 www.iosrjournals.org doi: 10.9790/487x-17411319 www.iosrjournals.org 13 | page
- * A study on issues and challenges of women empowerment in india dr. (smt.) rajeshwari m. shettar a thesis presented to the faculty of the graduate school of cornell university in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of master of arts by brooke shannan west august 2006
- *reviews of literature volume 1 , issue 7 / feb 2014 issn:-2347-2723 1 reviews of literature • volume 1 issue 7 • feb 2014 women empowerment in india: a study r. h. waghmode and j. l. kalyan
- *international center for research on women (icrw) 1120 20th street, nw suite 500 north washington, dc 20036 www.icrw.org tel: 202.797.0007 email: info@icrw.org

Violation of Women Rights: Religious and Statutory Protection in Bangladesh Perspective

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Abstracts:

Human rights refer such rights which a human being belong by birth, which is also inalienable and universal. A human life cannot be thought without basic human rights, which flourish the personality of the human being properly. It also provide a humanly life of a person. Unfortunately the women community is derived from getting basic human rights. This is the common perception that the women's community is the most vulnerable sector in a society. From the birth to death, in every stages of their life they have to face different form of violence, sometimes the form of violence is absolute. They are subjugated in every stages of their life by the male members of the family and kinsman. Sometimes it has forgotten that they are human being. There are no major changes between the period of pre-Islamic and modern era. The women are always suppressed for which different factors are responsible. The religious misinterpretation is one of the most vital causes of violating women rights. Islam honour the women as a human being without any discrimination, but illiteracy or blindness on religion the rights of the women violated day by day. Some people believe that Islam discriminate with the female community. This paper focuses on that, Islam never does so, but people misinterpreted it. This paper focuses on the rights granted by the Islam in reference with the pre Islamic condition of women. And draw a chronological chain of life how their rights are violating in every stage of their rights, by which it will make clear the fate and ultimate destination of women rights though there is statutory protection. This paper also focuses on statutory protection in the national and international perspective. Finally some recommendations has suggested to overcome from this situation, and to upheld the women human rights..

Key words: *Human rights, Women rights, Religious and statutory protection, State responsibility.*

"The history of mankind is a history of repeated injuries and usurpations on the part of a man towards a woman, having direct object the establishment of tyranny over her"¹

¹ Women's Rights Convention Manifesto, Seneca Falls, 1848. (The Seneca Falls Convention was the first women's rights convention. It advertised itself as "a convention to discuss the social, civil, and religious condition and rights of woman". Held in Seneca Falls, New York, it spanned two days over July 19–20, 1848).

Women's rights are those which are essential for physical, mental and spiritual development of a woman. Women have historically suffered injustice and discrimination, they oppressed and deprived in their own family, community and society at large. It's true that women's community is the most vulnerable sector in the society or a state.² Their rights are violating in every steps of their life and face different forms of violence. If we back to the pre-Islamic period where the women community was treated as goods, treated them humiliating.³ But Islam is the first religion which honoured, respect and granted the women rights as a human being. It has been studied the *Sura An Nissa, Attin, Al Mayeda* etc. of the holy Quran cover a wide range of women rights. Though rights are guaranteed but seldom had it ignored to implement. Beside the Holy Al Quran if we study the Hdith (sunnah)⁴, the Madina Sanad⁵ (first written constitution in the world) and the

speech of Bid day Hajj⁶ it will be much clear that how much Islam honour the women. In absence of proper religious knowledge the people are in the confusing situation regarding women rights. Sometimes they have to rely upon the religious head to take the opinion, unfortunately most of the time they misinterpret or neglect the women issue. Then they use the religion as a weapon to oppress the women. Later on when the concept of Muslim law has developed, the state itself comes forward to protect the rights of the women through enacting and implementing law. Like Muslim Family Law Ordinance, 1961, Dissolution of Muslim Marriages Act, 1939, and Family Court Ordinance, 1985 are landmark in granting the women's rights.

The paper is based on content analysis. In dealing with these issues, both primary and secondary sources have been taken into account. Relevant International Instruments, National Laws, case-laws, statements and official documents have been taken into account. Additionally secondary sources are including books, journals, articles; online resources,

²Dr.RabiaBhuiyan, *Gender and Tradition in Marriage & Divorce: An Analysis of Personal Laws of Muslims and Hindu Women in Bangladesh* (Dhaka: UNESCO) 2010, pp. 2.

³Md.AlamgirSirajuddin, *Muslim Family Law, secular courts & Muslim Women of South Asia*, Oxford University Press (1stedn. 2011) pp. 194.

⁴A report of the sayings or actions of Muhammad or his companions, together with the tradition of its chain of transmission.

⁵ The Charter of Medina or of Yathrib also known as the Constitution of Medina or of Yathrib was drafted by the Islamic prophet Muhammad shortly after his arrival at Medina (then known as Yathrib) in 622 CE (or 1 AH), following the Hijra from Mecca.

⁶ Shortly before his death, Prophet Muhammad delivered a sermon during theHajj, which came to be known as his "Final Sermon". This final sermon was not only a reminder to his followers, but also an important admonition. The final sermon confirms the end of his Prophetic Mission. He said, "O People, it is true that you have certain rights with regard to your women, but they also have rights over you. Remember that you have taken them as your wives only under a trust from God and with His permission".

statements; presented papers, documents of relevant international and non-governmental organizations and other materials have been taken into account for proper analysis, comprehensive understanding and consistent conclusion. In conducting legal research, the researcher depends on the documentary sources, information existing in forms of journal articles, case reports, legislation, records, etc., for analysis and conclusion. Accordingly the research is doctrinal in nature as no field work or empirical research has been undertake

The main objectives of this paper are the followings:

- a. To explore what are the Conflicts of Women Rights in Bangladesh.
- b. To analysis how Women Rights are violated in Bangladesh.
- b. To aware the People about Religious *i.e.* Islamic and Statutory Protection regarding Women Rights.

1. Pre Islamic Condition of Women:

Pre Islamic Condition of women was barbarous this period was known as *Ayem-e-Jahiliyah*.⁷ In that time the most

⁷The word Jahiliyah originated from Arabic root word 'jahala' and its derivatives, 'jahalun' and 'jahalatun' which mean 'lacking of knowledge' and 'astray' and 'ayem' means period. From the Koran, the jahiliyyah people is mentioned by any of these four characteristics: i) No prophecies and revelation (guidance); ii) No civilization; iii) The peoples have no good manner; iv) Referred as jahiliyyah because illiterate. Having said that, any people at any period of time which have at least

vulnerable and suppressive classes were women. 'Wine, women and wars were the only three objects that claimed the love and devotion of the Arab.'⁸ The birth of a daughter was the matter of shame and disgraceful for the family, in that's why they were buried alive.⁹ There was no specified or justified rules regarding marry or divorce. The husband would marry and divorce at his sweet wills. Divorce was pronounced three times and was effective instantly. Adultery was the common phenomena.¹⁰ Woman was simply treated as a goods, they had no legal rights, in youth they were goods and chattels of father after marry husbands became their lord. There was no space to evaluate them as human being. They were the burden of the family. They had no rights over the property, no rights to hold, posses, dispose or inherit the property. There was no systematic procedure to marry or divorce and also girls had no choice to marry. The marriage contract was the contract between the father and husband, who used to pay a sum of money to the father of the bride, thereby purchasing her and making her his exclusive property. Captured women were completely under the authority of their captors and sexually abused and exploited by them. There was no freedom of expression, education, choice...and so on. It was the period of superstitious and

one of these characteristics is also considered as jahiliyyah.

⁸KhudaBaksh, *Contributions to the History of Islamic Civilization* (1929) pp. 165.

⁹ Md. Alamgir (note 3) at 1.

¹⁰ Ibid.

idolatry and was treated as like as animal. So in a word Polygamy was universal, divorce was easy and buried of female infanticide was common.¹¹

2. Islam and Women Rights (Rights granted by Islam):

Every religion is kind and human regarding human life and rights, but Islam is more concern and humanitarian regarding women issues other than another religion. Islam honour the women as a human being, it not only respect the women but also protect their rights. It covers the whole range of life of every human being.

Right to be treated equally:

The woman is equal to man in bearing personal and common responsibilities and in receiving rewards for her deeds. She possesses an independent personality. Her human identity is neither inferior to nor deviant from that of man. Both are partner of one another. The Holy Quran provides clear cut evidence that women are completely equated with man in the sight of God in terms of her rights and responsibilities. The Quran states *“Every soul will be (held) in pledge for its deeds”*¹² And also says that, *“So their Lord accepted their prayers: I will not suffer to be lost the work of any of you whether male or*

*female. You precede one from another”*¹³ Woman is recognized by Islam as a full and full and equal partner of man in the procreation of humankind *“O mankind! Verily we have created you from a single (pair) of a male and a female and made you into nations and tribes that you may know each other”*¹⁴ in another verse it also has been cited that *“And their Lord has accepted (their prayers) and answered them (saying): Never will I cause to be lost the work of any of you, be he male or female: you are members, one of another”*¹⁵

Right to Upheld Human Dignity:

It is natural that every human being possesses some basic personality by born. One should respect the dignity of another. She is acknowledged as an independent personality, on possession of human qualities and worthy of spiritual aspiration.

Freedom of Expression:

Islam permits all the human being to express their opinion. The sound opinion of woman should take into consideration and cannot be disregarded because to belong the female sex. It is reported to Quran and history that the women not only expressed her opinion freely but also argued and participated in the

¹¹Selena Akter, A. N. M. ArifurRahman and MdJahidHossainDolon, *Muslim Law* (3rdedn, Hira Publications, Dhaka 2014) pp. 3.

¹²The Holy Al Quran 74:38

¹³Ibid. at 3:195

¹⁴ Ibid. at 49:13

¹⁵Ibid. at 3:195, 33-35 to 36.

decision or policy making.¹⁶ They also stood in opposition to the Caliphs.

Right to Choice of Marriage:

To arrange a valid marriage the consent of the both parties must have to be free. There is no room to force a woman to marry against her will.¹⁷ According to the holy Prophet, “*A widow is not to be married before her consent is sought*” and “*no virgin girl is to marry without first consulting her and her approval*”¹⁸ There is a story that a girl was forced by the father to marry a person she did not like, then prophet (pbuh)¹⁹ revoked this marriage and allowed her to marry a man of her choice.²⁰ Now it's very clear that everyone has the right to marry in his or her choice, no for the force marriage is permissible. If guardian done such then the part has the option to exercise option of puberty, where the party can either continue or repudiate the marital tie.²¹

Right to Property:

In Islam a women not only inherit the property but also own the property by purchase, gift, will, possesses, which

may be movable or immovable. She has the absolute right to enjoy, dispose and alienate the property. In case of inheritance a woman can inherit the property as a daughter, as a wife, as a mother, as a sister and so on. There are specific quranic provisions²² that every human being has the right to inheritance. Especially the women can inherit as a wife, as a daughter, as a mother and as a sister. She has the absolute control over the property which has been own by them.²³ Beside these women are women are entitle to get the proprietary protection through maintenance and dower.

Right to Participate in Public Life:

The historical record is clear that the women were participated in the public life, especially during the war; they were brought by the shoulder to serve the wounded soldiers.²⁴ They were not shut behind iron bars or considered worthless creatures and deprived of souls. Where *Hazrath Aiysha (RH)* opposed the Khalafate of two Khalifa, one is *H. Osman (RH)* and another is *H. Ali (RH)*. She participated in the war against *H. Ali (RH)* in Battle of Jamal or the Battle of Bassorah, where she commanded the shoulder directly which was held in

¹⁶Ibid. at 58:1-4 and 60:10-12.

¹⁷Selena Akter, *et al* (note 11) at 20.

¹⁸Saiyed Abdullah Al Hatimy, *women in Islam: A comparative study*, (Lahore, Islamic Publications Ltd. 1993) pp. 25.

¹⁹The Arabic phrase ‘alayhi as-salam’, which translates as "peace be upon him" is a conventionally complimentary phrase or durood attached to the names of the prophets in Islam.

²⁰Ibid. at 25.

²¹Khalid Rashid, *Muslim Law*, (4thedn. Eastern Book Company, 2004)pp.68.

²² The law of inheritance has been given in the Qur'an in *Surah Al-Nisaa* (the fourth chapter) verses 11 & 12 and then in verse 176. The number of Quranic sharers is 12 in which 8 are females.

²³The Holy Al Quran, 2:228.

²⁴ Dr.ZakirNaik, *Collection of all lectures with all answer of open questions* (Dhaka, 2ndedn. 2010) pp. 654.

November 656. In early Islamic history, Muslim women played a variety of public roles and certainly exercised property rights. The Prophet in his farewell sermon spoke of property rights for both men and women, and his wives held their own separate property. The first convert to Islam (*Khadija*), its first martyr (*Sumayya*), the first to grant refuge to the Prophet at Medina when he fled from persecution at Macca (*Umm Sa'id*), the keeper of the keys to the Holy *Ka'aba*, the custodian of the first copy of the *Qur'an* (*Hafsa*), the manager of the first hospital (*RafidahAslamiyya*), one of the *Imams* appointed to lead the prayers of both men and women (*Umm Waraqa*) and a superintendent at the market at *Madinah* (*Samra' bintNuhayak al-Asadiya*) were all women.²⁵

Right to Enter into Contract:

Islam gives the rights of women to own the property by inheritance by inheritance, gift, will, purchase and so on, having the absolute right over the property. In that's why to regulate the property, they has the legal right to enter in to the contract, to run a business, to inherit property from her husband, parents, sons or any kinsman, which she would own, and could possess or dispose of absolutely.²⁶

²⁵ Islam Land & property, Research series paper no 5, *Muslim Women and Property*, UNHABITAT (United Nations Human Settlement Programme) pp. 12 <Web: www.unhabitat.org> accessed on 10 October 2015.

²⁶ The Holy Al Quran,4:7.

Right to Education:

To be the best human being there is no alternative rather than education. Its' flourish a man to be an ideal one. Islam also emphasize on the education both man and women. The Holy Quran says that, "*Are the all equal, who knows or doesn't know*"?²⁷ Beside verse if we go through the Hadith then it will be clear that Hazrath Mohammad (sm) not only given the importance but also patronized the women education. Because he realized education is the foundation of all nation. It is mandatory for all Muslim man and women to acquire knowledge.²⁸ At the time of revelation of Islam there were only17 educated people, out of them 5 were women.²⁹ Prophet said again that, "*Who have more than one and educated them properly and merry them to the honest bride he will stay with me in heaven*"³⁰This is also remarkable that *Hazrath (SM)* fixed a in a week it teach the women, It is the great example that *Hazrath Aiyeshe (RH)* stated 2210 hadith were 174 placed in the Bukari Sharif as a shahih hadith. On the other hand *Hazrath Fatima (RH)* house was crowded by the people of education thirsty.³¹ So there is no doubt to say that Islam not only recognize the right to education of women but also implement it.

²⁷ The Holy Al Quran, 39: 9.

²⁸ IbneMaja(Al Hadith).

²⁹ Mohamman Abdul Munimkhan, *Islam appreciate the women education*,The Daily ProthomAlo, 12 September, 2014, pp. 12.

³⁰ Al hadith, Muslim.

³¹ Dr. Bhuiyan (note 2) at 20.

3. Statutory Protection:

Today's world is concern with the women rights, because they has suppressed historically. Time to time not only the government of Bangladesh but also international community has taken initiative to protect the women rights. Unfortunately it fails to fulfill the demand or to protect the women community from violence.

Women's Rights under the Constitution of the Peoples' Republic of Bangladesh:

The constitution is the supreme law of the land, the law which is inconsistent with constitution will be void.³² While Bangladesh constitution has protected women's rights under broad fundamental rights and universal principles of equality and participation for all citizens, yet there are certain provisions in Bangladesh constitution. Such as ensure representation of women in local government institution,³³ ensure participation of women in all spheres of national life,³⁴ State shall not discriminate against any citizen on grounds only of religion, race, sex, or place of birth, and women shall equal rights with men in all spheres of the state and of public life, the state shall make special laws for advancement of women.³⁵ The constitution also provides that a woman has the right to seek

nomination and contest for any political opposition.

Women's Rights under National Laws:

The General Law consists of civil and criminal laws, which are governed respectively by the Code of Civil Procedure of 1908, the Penal Code of 1860 and the Criminal Procedure Code of 1898. The Personal or Family Laws are under the General Law but mostly are governed by the civil law; the matters which directly affect women such as marriage, divorce, dower, maintenance, guardianship, custody, inheritance and restitution of conjugal rights are separately governed by each religious community's "religious personal law" system. For example, take marriage. Muslim parties, says Pereira, are regulated by, among others, the Muslim Family Ordinance, 1961 provides punishment in case of polygamy and divorce in violation of statutory provisions, the Muslim Marriages and Divorce (Registration) Act, 1974 makes mandatory to register the marriage and divorce, Dowry Prohibition Act, 1980 (amended in 1986) prohibit dowry and provide the strict punishment, Child Marriage Restraint Act, 1929(amended in 1984) insert the punishment to marry any girl who is under the age of majority, Family Courts Ordinance, 1985, Women and Children Anti Repression Act, 2000(amended in 2003), The Acid Crime Control Act, 2011, The Children Act, 2013 all are widely concern about the women rights and inflict the strong punishment in case of violating the

³²Article 7 of the Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.

³³Ibid. Article 9.

³⁴Ibid. Article 10.

³⁵Ibid. Article 28.

provisions of law. The overall character of this new law is reflective of same level of participatory effort; the law on children is one of the best examples of the workings of a clear distinction between religion as a private matter and the area of personal welfare of citizens as subject to state intervention. The laws on children and personal disputes relating to children such as the Guardians and Wards Act, the Majority Act and the Child Marriage Restraint Act, are all applied uniformly to all children and citizens of Bangladesh, irrespective of gender or religion despite these areas being clearly within religious-personal sphere of citizen's lives.

4. International Instruments:

The women rights are not the concern of national but today's world is concern more to protect the women rights. Since the founding of the United Nations, equality between men and women has been among the most fundamental guarantees of human rights. Adopted in 1945, the Charter of the United Nations sets out as one of its goals "*to reaffirm faith in fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth of the human person, and in the equal rights of men and women*".³⁶The essential rights have been incorporated in international bill of rights and women bill of rights, The Convention on the Elimination of All

Forms of Discrimination against Women, 1979 (Hereafter CEDAW). Bangladesh continues to maintain reservations Articles 2 and 13(a). In September 2000, Bangladesh became the first country to ratify the Optional Protocol to CEDAW which ensures the implementation of the tools to eradicate discrimination. Maintaining such reservation to the very pledge to eradicate such discrimination is therefore contradictory and makes the sincerity of the state to remove gender discrimination, questionable.

Under Article 2, states are required to domestically enforce CEDAW, adopt appropriate legislation and other measures to prohibit all discrimination against women, modify or abolish existing laws, regulations, customs and practices which constitute such discrimination. Other articles of the Convention deal with many of the pressing issues that concern women such as women's right to determine their own and their children's nationality and removal of discrimination in education, employment, healthcare, social and economic benefits.

Part IV of CEDAW calls for equality before the law and equality within marriage and family law. Articles under this component for example guarantees the same legal capacity as men to contract, administer property, appear in courts or before tribunals; freedom of movement the right to choose where they will live; equal rights and responsibilities of women with men in marriage; the

³⁶ Women's Rights are Human Rights, UN<
<http://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Publications/H R-PUB-14-2.pdf>> accessed on 15 October 2015.

right to choose when they will have children, to choose their family name or occupation; and equal rights and responsibilities regarding ownership, management and disposition of property. So ultimately the goal of the CEDAW cannot be gained by restricting thus articles. So it can be said in a sense that the CEDAW is inactive in Bangladesh.

Bangladesh acceded to the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) in 1998 with a number of declarations. The interpretative declaration relating to Articles 2 and 3 of the Covenant states that equality of rights between men and women is to be implemented in so far as they agree with the Constitution of Bangladesh and, more specifically, subject to Bangladeshi state inheritance law. Bangladesh acceded to the Convention on Consent to Marriage, Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriages in 1998 with reservations to Articles 1 and 2, stating that the treaty would be applied in accordance with the Personal Laws of different religious communities of the country, and allowing for a dispensation as to age, for serious reasons, in the interest of the intending spouses.

Bangladesh also signed and ratified the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR). Article 3 of the said Instrument stated that the parties to the present covenant undertake to ensure the equal right of men and women to the enjoyment of all civil and political rights set forth in the present covenant. It also

inserted that the right to life of every human being,³⁷ and all persons are equal before law and are entitled without any discrimination to the equal protection of the law, no discrimination on any ground such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status.³⁸

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights provides that everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person,³⁹ and all are equal before law and are entitle without any discrimination to equal protection of law, are entitle to equal protection against discrimination in violation of this declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination.⁴⁰ Beside this every human being has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and wellbeing of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social service, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control.⁴¹

New laws have to be formulated to reflect Bangladesh's concurrence with international laws such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and

³⁷Article 6 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.

³⁸ Ibid. Article 26.

³⁹Article 3 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

⁴⁰ Ibid. Article 7.

⁴¹ Ibid. Article 25.

CEDAW. While religion and culture have to be respected, violations of basic human rights in the name of religion or tradition must be categorically condemned and shunned by the laws of the land. Most importantly laws that govern both public and personal spheres must be compatible to the Constitutional laws and be equally applicable to all citizens irrespective of sex, religion or the community they belong to.

5. The Present Condition of Female in Bangladesh:

The female community is the most vulnerable not only in the Bangladesh but also in the subcontinent. They have to suffer in every stages of their life in different forms and ways. The whole life passed away with a tragedy. It can be described in the way of stages how they have to face different form of violence in every steps of life. Here a chain of violence has been presented which will make clear what a life lead by the women community in Bangladesh! Though there are religious and statutory provisions.

a. Before Birth: when she is in the mother womb the discrimination or violation of the human rights has started. If the father informed that the upcoming baby is girl through ultra sonography then abortion taken place, misbehaving with the wife has started. Islam clearly prohibit killing of human being. The holy Al Quran state that, *Kill not your children for fear of want: we shall provide*

*sustenance for them as well for you. Verily the killing of them is a great sin*⁴² beside these it's also punishable offence under Bangladesh Penal Code.

- b. After Birth: If birth taken place started the discrimination, the father or the parents are not happy if the mother giving birth a baby girl. The torture and discrimination started towards the new mother and new baby, they deprive from getting proper nourishment or natal care from other family member. Though Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh prohibit the discrimination on any grounds.
- c. Childhood: Discrimination with brother in respect of schooling, feeding, dressing and so on. The son is always in the preferable position in the family. Because the family member believe that son is the future leader of the family, he will takes all the responsibilities of the family where the daughter have to go to the another family. So investment to the girl is loss project.
- d. Adolescent: The girl is not secure inside or outside the house. Sexual harassment by near relatives (like cousin, uncle) then outsider is placed first in the life of little adolescent girl. In this case they cannot disclose it, if disclosed the parents scold her rather than taking initiative against the offender. She deprived from getting mental support from parents, which is not prepare to accept it,

⁴² The Holy Al Quran, 17: 31.

- ultimately mental disaster taken place and she lost the confidence, faith and trust on the family, society and herself.
- e. **Eve Teasing:** The worst evil in our society is eve teasing. Where teenage boys, rickshaw pullers, bus drivers, street vendors, traffic vendors and colleagues or supervisor of working women making sexual harassment against the women.⁴³ Almost 90 percent of girls aged 10-18 have undergone the experience.⁴⁴ The impact of eve teasing are drop out from school, early marriage, socio economic insecurity and commit suicide. It has been reported that 12 percent girls committed suicide in cause of eve teasing.⁴⁵
- f. **Child Marriage:** Early marriage is another obstacle in promoting women's rights. The Majority Act, 1875 clearly provides that a woman must at least be 18 years of age to be able to get married. Fear of poverty, perceptions of family honour and social insecurity are some of the major reasons behind early marriages. After dropping from the school, unconsciousness of the guardian arranges marriage of the little girl without her choice, which is not only injurious for her mental situation but also her health.⁴⁶ It's alarming that last year 1237 child marriage arranged whose age is not more than 15 years.⁴⁷ By getting early marriage the brides deprived from getting dower, maintenance and so on. Someone proposed to continue to study but after marriage the reality is different.⁴⁸ The consequence of the child marriage is depriving the female from economic empowerment, which she has to bear whole life because the treatment of empowered and no empowered women in our society is different and it is the reality.
- g. **Child Motherhood:** It's the fundamental right to know about the reproductive health. Absence of sufficient knowledge about the reproductive health is the common phenomena in our society. So it's the highly risk for new born baby and mother. There is no scope of safe maternity, ultimate a child given birth a malnutrition child ultimately the malnutrition nation.
- h. **Demand of Dowry:** After passing sometimes the new violence started.

⁴³Camellia Khan, 'Eve Teasing in Bangladesh: Social & Legal Perspective', ASA University Review Centre for Socio Economics Research, vol 9, no-1, 16th issue, Jan-June 2015, para 1&4.

⁴⁴ Bangladesh National Women's Lawyers Association (BNWLA) *81% Girls Fall Victim to Eve Teasing- Study*, BNWLA, July 2008 <<http://www.bnwla.org.bd/content/view/186/large,enl>> accessed on 17 October 2015.

⁴⁵ UNICEF Early Marriage: Child Spouses, Report No-7, UNICEF March 2001. Centre for social Research (CSR) "CSR Story" CSR <<http://www.csrindia.org/story.html>> accessed on 20 October 2015.

⁴⁶ Staff Correspondent, *The Effect of Early Marriage*, The Daily ProthomAlo 10 October 2015, pp.21.

⁴⁷ Staff correspondent, *The Child Marriage At 15*, The Daily ProthomAlo, 15 October 2015, pp. 1.

⁴⁸ Staff correspondent, *What a protest !* The Daily ProthomAlo, 11 September 2015, pp. 20.

The bridegroom and his family demand dowry, otherwise the physical and mental torture take place in the life of wife. Sometimes husband divorced the wife or killed the wife by torturing is the ultimate destination of the failed wife. At the stake of life the father's family refuses to give the shelter for a few days. Then she has to pass another miserable life.

- i. Physical and mental Torture: Still today husband and his family cannot think the wife as a better half; they cannot treat them as a human being. The husband and the other member of the family torture physically and mentally in lame excuse. Husband think that wife is the property of the husband and he has the absolute control over her. so he can treat the wife as his sweet will.
- j. At the Aged: By facing above all situation in every stage of life they have no meaning of life and think that this is life. At the aged they lead another miserable and destitute life. Now they are the burden to the son's family if son's give the shelter, otherwise they have no shelter to pass away the rest of life.
- k. Inheritance: Islam entitles the women to inherit the property. It has been clearly stated in the Holy Quran that the men and the women entitle to take the share which has been leave by their parents or near relations according to their determined share which may be little or much. "*For men is a share of that which parents and near relations leave, and for*

women is a share of that which parents and near leave, whether it be little or much a determined share".⁴⁹

So a woman can inherit the property from father, mother, husband, son, daughter and grandson. They have the absolute rights over the inherited property. But the fact is different-maximum women of Bangladesh cannot take the possession or enjoy the property which inherited from father; they cannot do so because they think they has to go to the brother's house for nayar (a trip to brothers house). If they claim then they will be hurt and will not look after in any crisis. The women believe that they have maintained good relations with their brothers and they fell that their family had already given them their fair share of family property by paying a dowry.⁵⁰ Eventually if any woman claim that property then the brother will not give her the property in same place, but given to different part in different places. On the other hand any property inherits from the deceased husband enjoyed by the son's to whom she stays.

All the violence stated above are the violation of statutory laws and religious obligations. So the people should think that it not only sin but also punishable offence. So people should think, feel and believe in women rights. It's not only the religious and statutory obligations but

⁴⁹ The Holy Al Quran, 4:8.

⁵⁰ Dr. Bhuiyan (note 2) at 25.

also the moral obligations. Otherwise our society can never be developed. Because its' quit impossible to develop the nation by ignoring one side of the whole community.

6. Recommendations:

1. The change should begin with individual, the mentality of Parents and other family members should change. Because family is the first place for take shelter of every girl and women. So they should about the women's rights, and they have to feel the violation of women rights is not only religious obligation but also statutory obligations. For this purpose awareness programme like Meena cartoon may broadcast in the Television Channel. The government and Non-Government Organization may sponsor more financial investment to telecast this program to aware the people about the women rights.

2. Education is the most important weapon to nourish or flourish the full human personality, by which a person can justify what is right and wrong, what he should do or should not do. And be aware about their rights and duties. So government can provide education in easy and accessible way. Education can empower the women financially, mentally and spiritually.

3. Islam treats the women as a human being, and honour with full dignity and guaranteed the women rights for their development. The rights granted by the Islam should circulate positively; it only

can be done by the religious leaders. For this purpose, at first the training should arrange for the religious leaders to whom the mass people relay and seek opinion on the religious issues. So to prevent the violation of women rights the positive motivation of the religious leaders are very important.

4. Though there are so many updated laws regarding women issues, and there is a strict provision of punishment in case of violating women rights. But the nature of the patriarchal society never be changed, they rapidly violating the women rights, still today they cannot think the women as a human being. So enactment and enforcement of the strict laws could prevent the violence against women and ensure the women rights.

5. Financial empowerment is very important, because the financially empowered women treated differently rather than non-empower one. The first one has the voice in the family; their opinion can be taken into consideration in the family. Where statutory and religious law provides the women to become empower financially through inheritance, maintenance, dower gift, will, purchase and so on. Beside these they have the right to work which should be properly remunerated while having the rights as to equal pay for equal work. So state can encourage and create the scope or opportunity of work for the women which may reduce the violation of women rights.

6. Fatwa (the opinion of the religious head in the society) is the weapon to oppress the women and violate the women rights.⁵¹ Because most of the

⁵¹Dr. Bhuiyan (note 2) at 211.

time misinterprets the religious matters especially regarding women issues. By exercising fatwa they not only violate the women rights but also violate the religious norms and the statutory laws, though higher judiciary pronounce a judgment that only learned person can exercise fatwa by which they cannot inflict physical and mental punishment. Whether it will be obeyed or not by the opinion seeker it will solely depend upon the sweet will of them. But the reality is different. In that's why the Government should pass an act to prohibit the Fatwa so that nobody can misuse it to violate women rights.

7. Bangladesh has sufficient laws to protect the women rights, but there is no monitoring body to monitor whether the law enforcing agency and implementing agency act properly or not. So government may establish a independent and neutral monitoring body to protect the women rights.

8. The government may include in the text book chapter of the primary to higher secondary about the women rights in the religious and statutory perspective. The positive motivation is necessary about the women rights to think that they are not burden but they may be asset of family, society and state.

9. The law enforcing agency or the government may establish the one stop service to provide the emergency and prompt service to the victim. In that purpose police, Rapid Action Battallion may be engaged as a separate wing to support the victim.

At last it can be says that it will not be wise to say that only the government is sufficient to prevent the violence against women, Beside the government the non-

government organization, that individual members of the society have to come forward to ensure women rights. The family and the society can play vital role to treat the women as human being.

7. Concluding Remark:

Women are universally sought after in literature and Bangladeshi women are no exception. The beauty and charms of Bangladeshi women are celebrated in poems, legends and short stories. But the suffering of Bangladeshi women is often ignored. Too many still face deprivation and oppression and the legal and socio-economic system does not do enough to prevent discrimination and violence against women. However, despite such legal support, Bangladeshi women are still not receiving equal treatment in practice. Inequalities are common. Though religion and the statutory law treat the men and women equally, but the reality is different, women suffer degrading treatment as children and as wives from guardians and husband respectively. The truth is that women are treated as personal properties, possessed and controlled by the guardians and the husbands, the family should think that the female are human being. They have the rights to be treated humanely. We have to think that they are the asset of the family, society and state. The journey or struggling to protect the girls rights should started from the family and society. For this purpose the Government, Non-Government Organization and International Organization must come forward to aware the people and taking proper steps to protect the women rights. So we should remember that, "*Their lives God where women are respected*" (Manu Smiriti).